

Ir0000014 – Itserr

White paper: Report on Digital Archives on Ancient Religious Content (DARCAR)

Document reference:	ITSERR-D.10.1-DARCAR	
Version number:	01.01	
Status:	FINAL	
Last revision date:	05/12/2024	by: Andrea D'Andrea, Gilda Ferrandino, Alexia Pavan
Verification date:	30/11/2024	by: UNIOR
Approval date:	DD/MM/YYYY	by: MUR
Subject:	IR0000014 – ITSERR White paper: Report on Digital Archives on Ancient Religious Content	
Filename:	ITSERR_D10.1_DARCAR_02.00_FINAL	

This research has been funded by the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)

Mission 4 – Component 2 under the project ITSERR Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE

CUP B53C22001770006 Ir00000014

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Change history

Version Number	Date	Status	Summary of main or important changes
00.01	15/09/2023	WORKING	Working version
00.02	27/10/2023	DRAFT	Complete revision of the document after ITSERR Board review
01.00	22/04/2024	FINAL	Finalisation
02.00	05/12/2024	FINAL	Minor revisions

Distribution List

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This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
ITSERR-WP10_Deliverables\D10.1_DARCAR\

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1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

The main goal of WP₁₀ ReTINA is the enhancement of the RESILIENCE infrastructure through the creation of religious content datasets from ancient world sites along and around the Nile Valley. ReTINA tackles a gap in the digital description and fruition of ancient religious texts from archaeological contexts through the implementation of a shared data model and the creation of a prototype software for fruition. The specificity of the field of religious studies, where the cultural significance of texts and objects must often be linked to specific theological factors, allows for the consideration of descriptors that go beyond the merely linguistic and religious level and can lay the groundwork for the creation of further digitization work. ReTINA will strength RESILIENCE by supplying of research-enhancing services, especially those dedicated to digitisation tools.

The Nile Valley case study represents a microcosm that can be extended to other equally (or more) fragmented contexts. Therefore, ReTINA aims to increase knowledge and understanding of religious texts and objects outside the Nile Valley as well.

Starting from a review of the state of the art, a data model will be designed. The schema will be consistent with the main international metadata standards, taxonomies and thesauri and will be published as Open Data and/or Linked Open Data to encourage the spread of the principles of FAIR data and, more generally, of Open Science in this area of study. The goal will be achieved through the completion of several steps, examining digital datasets already directly available online.

Digital archives will be able to be compared and integrated through semantic and syntactic interoperability ensured by the adoption of a data model based on international metadata. Texts, appropriately transliterated, and objects belonging to the religious sphere, will be annotated by users who will also be able to view the media in 3D and have precise information about the materials used as well as the meanings.

1.2 Scope

This report describes schemas, metadata and taxonomies found in a selected list of existing digital archives on ancient religious texts coming from different times, regions, languages and supports. The paper falls within the activities of the task A_{10.1}. The outcomes of the survey will form the basis for the implementation of the next tasks aimed at developing a data-model (A_{10.2}) and at designing new methods and tools for image processing and linguistic analysis of ancient religious objects (A_{10.3}).

Three main issues have hindered the work of this task: firstly, the lack of digital infrastructures and repositories tailored to specific type of ancient religious content; the extreme variety of languages and writing forms envisaged by the project; and finally, the absence of semantic tools developed specifically for cataloguing and processing ancient religious texts.

The report has been carried out mainly focusing the following topics:

- Analysis of existing online datasets which include digitized images and texts on the Nile Valley and beyond
- Evaluation of already developed metadata standards, taxonomies, and thesauri to classify and catalogue ancient text and objects coming from the south Mediterranean area
- Review of the conclusions drawn from the primary digital projects in Egyptology, with a particular focus on the advancement of tools for data annotation and 3D visualization.

1.3 Report on the Digital Archives

Data and context appear to be two decisive factors for the implementation of a Resilience component aimed at the fruition of digital archives comprising complex, rare and/or endangered religious texts written in various media (stone, papyrus, etc.) from the Nile Valley and beyond. In addition, data and context are two key pillars for the design and development of tools to support scholars in specific expertise.

Over time, there has been a growing awareness of the need to employ descriptive standards to enable the preservation, understanding, and reuse of data. Numerous semantic technologies have been developed with the goal of facilitating data search and archive integration. In parallel, documentation has been developed providing a guidance on best practices for archaeological data management. Publishing data online involves a variety of decisions:

- what standards to use
- what types of data to publish
- what licenses to use to ensure reuse of data
- how to guarantee an easy access to data

The survey of existing online resources aimed to identify the semantic tools chosen for publishing and making collections accessible.

The scopes were:

- Understating how to extract subset of data concerning religious sphere
- Evaluating how these online sources (repositories, infrastructures, websites) handle any semantic tools
- Analyzing the use and application of the FAIR recommendations

The analysis started by investigating major European museums and then expanded to other non-European cultural institutions that preserve archaeological and epigraphic materials from the Nile Valley and beyond and exhibit their collections online. Some of these institutions have datasets restricted to their collections, while others, having participated in larger projects, are embedded in portals that provide numerous services for guided access to archaeological objects. Some keywords, such as “religious”, “sacred”, “devotional”, “ceremonial”, “texts”, and “inscriptions” combined in a different way by means of the logical connectors, were used to identify online collections of objects on ancient religious content from Nile Valley.

Each selected website has been catalogued according to the following data:

- The name and the URL of the institution and/or the project
- The availability of different languages to navigate and obtain information
- The policies related to the datasets access and download
- The use of metadata and vocabularies to standardize the datasets

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- The licenses for data-reuse, the type of available data (text, images, photos, drawings, 3D survey) and the format
- The compatibility with FAIR principles

At the end of the survey about 40 sites including ancient religious data from the Nile Valley were investigated.

This number has not been considered exhaustive as the selection was based on some criteria previously mentioned.

Some digital archives have been identified by means of websites that collect databases, such as the web platform Limo of KU Leuven, which allows one to search a wide variety of scientific sources and to browse many different resource types: printed and electronic books, electronic databases, journals, digital documents, and others, such as audiovisual material.

Another useful website we utilised in our search is Open Image Collections, which is generally effective for locating collections of digital images. The primary objective of this web platform is to guide users to these sources and promote their efficient and suitable utilisation for educational and non-commercial purposes. The website gathers digital image sources not only from agencies, designers, and artists but also from museums and institutions that have made their collections accessible for educational, scholarly, research, and recreational purposes. Such websites facilitate the process of searching for our survey and reduce the fragmentation of the sources on the Web. The analysis of the datasets has led to some reflections on the management of archaeological data.

Regrettably, not all technical details regarding the archive implementation were accessible on the website, particularly those concerning the chosen data model and semantic technologies employed. In certain instances, this information could only be obtained by referring to the bibliography. More comprehensive technical insights are typically available in the documentation of extensive projects or from initiatives focused on the study of a specific subject.

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1.4 Analysis of Digital Archives

LINE	TITLE	N° LANGUAGES	PASSWORD ACCESS	METADATA STANDARD	VOCABULARIES	LICENSE	DOWNLOAD	DATA TYPE	FAIR	URI
1	ISAC Integrated Database Project (IDB)	1	no	NA	NA	©	yes	images, pdf	NA	yes
2	Museo Egizio	2	no	no	no	CC BY 2.0	yes	images	no	no
3	Turin Papyrus Online Platform (TPOP)	2	yes	NA	yes	CC BY- NC	yes	images (TIFF), pdf, xlsx	NA	yes
4	MuseiD-Italia	2	no	yes	yes	CCo 1.0	yes, only metadata	images	no	no
5	Corpus of Ptolemaic Inscriptions	1	no	yes	yes	NA	no	text	no	yes
6	Museum	1	no	yes	yes	NA	no	images	NA	yes
7	Papyri.info	1	yes	yes	yes	CC	yes	xml	NA	yes
8	PAThs	1	no	yes	yes	CC BY- NC 4.0	NA	NA	NA	yes
9	Mummy Label Database	1	no	yes	NA	NA	yes	xml	NA	no
10	Corpus Louvre	1	no	yes	NA	©; CC 4.0; etalab 2.0	yes	images	NA	yes

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11	Ancient World Digital Library	1	no	yes	no	variable	no	pdf	yes	yes
12	Arachne	2	no	yes	yes	CC BY-NC-ND 3.0	NA	images	yes	yes
13	Project Karnak	3	no	NA	NA	NA	no	texts, images	NA	yes
14	The Arnold Meijer Archives of Egyptian Art	1	no	no	no	NA	no	images	no	no
15	DASI	1	no	yes	yes	©	no	image, texts	no	no
16	Egyptology Books and Articles in PDF online	1	no	no	no	CC	yes	pdf	no	no
17	Propylaeum	1	no	yes	yes	CC	yes	pdf	no	yes
18	Kelsey Museum Artifact Database University of Michigan	1	no	NA	NA	CC; only 49 closed	yes	images	no	no
19	Mudira Bilddatenbak	1	no	NA	no	©	no	images	no	no
20	Project Coptos	1	no	no	no	CC-BY-SA.	no	texts	no	no
21	Penn Museum	1	no	NA	yes	CC-BY-3.0	yes	csv, xml, json, images	NA	yes
22	Database of Medieval Nubian Texts	1	no	no	yes	NA	no	NA	no	yes
23	Beta Masāḥeft	4	no	yes	yes	CC BY 4.0	yes	images	yes	yes

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24	DEChrim	1	no	NA	yes	NA	yes	json	NA	yes
25	BerlPap	2	no	NA	yes	©	no	images, text	no	yes
26	Brooklyn Museum	1	yes	NA	NA	CC BY	yes	images	NA	yes
27	British Museum	1	no	yes	yes	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	yes	images	NA	yes
28	The Musawwarat Graffiti Archive	1	no	no	no	CC BY-SA 4.0	yes	images	no	no
29	Die Aegyptiaca der Universität Göttingen im Sammlungsportal	1	no	yes	yes	CC BY 4.0	yes only xml	images	no	yes
30	The Griffith Institute Archive	1	no, there is the possibility to login	yes	NA	©	yes only xml	image, pdf	no	yes
31	Princeton University Art Museum	1	no	NA	no	©	yes	images	yes	yes
32	The Walters Art Museum	1	no	yes	yes	CCo	yes	images, pdf	NA	yes
33	The Israel Museum	1	no	no	no	©	yes	pdf	no	no
34	Art Institute of Chicago Collections	1	no	NA	NA	CCo	yes	images	NA	yes
35	LACMA	1	no	no	no	variable	yes	images tiff, jpg, video, audio	no	no

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36	University Cambridge Digital Library	1	no	yes	NA	CC BY-NC 3.0	yes	images, metadata	yes	yes
37	The Metropolitan Museum of Arts	1	no	yes	no	CCo	yes	images	yes	yes
38	National Museum of Antiquities	10	no	NA	NA	CCo	yes	images	NA	yes
39	The Arabic Papirology Database	1	no	NA	yes	NA	NA	text	no	no
40	Trismegistos	1	yes	NA	yes	CC BY-SA 4.0	yes	csv, json	no	yes

Table 1 Digital Archives

1.5 Results

The survey looked at resources stored in aggregators, digital libraries, or simple databases. In some cases, a hierarchical database has been accessed directly from the portal, such as the Arnold Meijer Archives of Egyptian Art, the Mudira Bilddatenbak, Project Coptos, and the Database of Medieval Nubian Texts. The datasets are often displayed as simple tables; search engines appear limited to keywords. Data can also be accessed using metadata-based facets corresponding mostly to the Dublin Core schema. More information and documentation on the data management process are provided Beta Masāheft, PATHs, and Trismegistos. The examination of repositories and infrastructures, which offer a range of services, has revealed a certain level of challenge in comprehending the data. Despite the adoption of standard metadata and thesauri, particularly by aggregators, the data descriptions often appear inadequate, brief, or incomplete due to the frequent usage of only one language, or at most two, and the absence, in many instances, of images or thumbnails. These factors restrict the potential reuse of data. Moreover, data openness often extends solely to descriptive metadata, with images frequently subject to restrictive licenses. From the perspective of preserving a specific dataset, these limitations may have a minimal short-term impact as they fulfil the requirements of a particular project or institution tasked with digitization and preservation. However, when contemplating future reuse, such choices can pose challenges. These limitations don't ensure the quality of datasets or their effective reuse, particularly concerning the potential utilization of these resources for training AI applications in the future. Despite the mandate to align their repositories with FAIR principles, the survey revealed that only a small fraction of the published datasets fully adhere to these guidelines. Consequently, datasets were categorized into three groups based on their adherence to FAIR principles: datasets that are fully compatible with FAIR recommendations, datasets structured with a standard data model but not entirely compliant with FAIR principles, and datasets that do not meet FAIR criteria at all.

An Excel file was created to summarize the results of the survey conducted according to WP requirements. In the table, the symbol "NA" (not available) was used to indicate the absence of information on the technical process, while the expression "not available" identifies the lack of references even in the bibliography listed on the websites.

1.5.1 Data Search

Online collections are accessible and searchable based on a limited number of criteria, which vary for each portal. Typically, search engines include a search box designed to locate one or more keywords using logical operators such as AND/OR.

The results are usually listed individually and linked to the webpage of the specific resource. According to the characteristics of the portal, there is the possibility to apply one or more filters, facets, or other options. The search for religious texts appeared difficult.

The use of keywords such as "religious," "text(s)," and "inscription(s)," along with filters like Place, Time, or Culture, doesn't consistently aggregate all anticipated results. Instead, it often retrieves records where both the specified words and filters are present in the metadata. This outcome is contingent upon how materials are described and the application of metadata or controlled vocabularies. This approach aids in identifying specific and pertinent objects within a given collection. An exception is Trismegistos, which is an interdisciplinary portal that focuses on the Nile Valley and in particular on texts coming from this region; or projects which focus on a specific culture such as the DBMNT, PATHs, Beta Masāheft, University Cambridge Digital Library and Papyri.info.

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In the case of DBMNT, as depicted in Figure 1, users have the capability to filter results and choose multiple text types from the dropdown menu. Additionally, they can utilize logical operators such as AND/OR to conduct more refined searches. Furthermore, it is possible to filter the languages of the texts. The results are presented in a list format indicating the primary information. The chosen resource from the list (Figure 2) is displayed in a supplementary section where a link to Trismegistos provides the URI and webpage of the resource (Figure 3).

The screenshot shows the DBMNT search interface. On the left, there is a 'DETAILED SEARCH' section with input fields for 'DBMNT text no.', 'TM text no.', 'Provenance', 'Region', and 'Findspot'. A dropdown menu is open, showing options like 'document: legal', 'document: letter', 'document: list', 'document: official', 'epitaph', 'foundation inscription', 'invocation', 'legend', 'literary', and 'literary: epigraphical'. On the right, there are filters for 'Language' and 'Content', with another dropdown menu open showing options like 'Arabic', 'Coptic', 'Coptic or Greek', 'Coptic or Old Nubian', and 'Greek'. Below the search filters, a table displays the search results.

▼ DISPLAYED BELOW					
1292	/ Qasr Ibrim	/ 1000–1399	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Psalm 149–150
1319	/ Qasr el-Wizz	/ 900–999	/ Greek/Coptic/Old Nu...	/ literary: biblical	/ Daniel 3:57–81 (Benedicite) + subs...
1365	/ Dongola	/ 900–1299	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Psalm 29
1388	/ Dongola	/ 1000–1299	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Psalm 103:15–31
1389	/ Dongola	/ 1000–1299	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Daniel 3:31–34, 38–40
1393	/ Naq' el-Oqba	/ 1000–1399	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Psalm 33:2–5
1985	/ Dongola	/ 1000–1399	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ literary: biblical	/ Psalm 128 (127)
2739	/ unknown	/ 1000–1399	/ Greek/Old Nubian	/ liturgical: prayer	/ fragment of baptismal liturgy

Figure 1 DBMNT search page.

Figure 2 The returned list of DBMNT

In many online collections of museums, the search by each culture (e.g. Egyptian) and type of objects (e.g. texts, inscriptions) produced more results than the keywords. However, the returned list has to be reviewed and the resources of interest have to be manually selected.

One aspect that appears to be not considered enough is the thematic categorization of resources. Only in five cases exists a filter which allows to select the religious documents: ISAC Integrated Database project (in Object Type "religious/ceremonial", in Type "Religious"), Museum (in Object Work Type "religious text") Propylaeum (in Subject "religion" and "religious aspect"), British Museum

The screenshot shows the detailed view of a resource. At the top, there are navigation arrows and the text 'Text 1002'. Below that, there is a 'Stable url' field and a link to 'Trismegistos text.369556'. A horizontal menu contains tabs for 'BASIC INFO', 'TECHNICAL INFO', 'CHRONOLOGY', 'NAMES', 'OFFICES & TITLES', 'TOPONYMS & ETHNONYMS', 'ILLUSTRATION', 'BIBLIOGRAPHY', 'CONCORDANCES', and 'RELATED'. The 'BASIC INFO' tab is active, showing the following details:

Provenance	Qasr Ibrim	Medium	manuscript: leaf
Region	Nobadia	Technique	painted
Findspot	cathedral (church 293), nave, in dust above pavement	Type of text	liturgical: lectionary
Excavation no.		Language	Greek/Old Nubian
Present location	unknown	Content	fragment of Psalter (Psalm 61:10–13; 83:2–12)
Museum no.		Date	1000–1399
		Notes	the same hand as P. QI II 12 & 13 (DBMNT 1009, 1010);

Figure 3 Section dedicated to the selected resource

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(in Subject “religion/belief” and “religious object”) and Art Institute of Chicago Collection (in Artwork Type “religious/ritual object” and in Subject “religious scenes” and “religious”).

The thematic classification may depend on the interest of the research project that prefers to focus on some aspects or on the functionality, thus a classification on period, place, material, and media type is preferred.

The screenshot shows a search results page for the query "text". The URL is [https://isac-idb.uchicago.edu/results.php?tab=MC&q=\(text\)+&sort=score+desc&start=0&rows=50&wt=json&facet=true&facet.mincount=1](https://isac-idb.uchicago.edu/results.php?tab=MC&q=(text)+&sort=score+desc&start=0&rows=50&wt=json&facet=true&facet.mincount=1). The search results are sorted by Relevance, showing 1 - 50 of 1260 results on Page 1, with 50 results per page.

Search filters include: Research Archives, **Museum Collection**, Museum Archives, Epigraphic Survey, Digital Archives, and CAMEL.

Results shown:

- Coin (Cast)**: Description: Rayy coin cast. RH5295. Coin legend in Arabic, center text almost illegible. Includes a thumbnail image.
- Ostrakon**: Description: Literary, inscribed in black ink on obverse only. Religious. Material: Clay, Baked. Dimensions: 83X55X8 MM. Inscribed: Yes. Country: Egypt. Place/site: Thebes. Period: New Kingdom. Date: --. Registration Number: E25326.
- Ostrakon**: Description: Literary, inscribed in black ink on obverse only. Religious. Material: Clay, Baked. Dimensions: 100X55X10 MM. Inscribed: Yes. Country: Egypt.

The "Refine Results" sidebar on the right includes the following filters:

- Object Type**
 - Classification Broad
 - Inscription
 - Inscribed
 - Yes (77)
 - No (9)
 - Language
 - Egyptian (40)
 - Akkadian Language (26)
 - Sumerian (2)
 - Hebrew (1)
 - Sumerian, Akkadian (1)
 - Type
 - Literary (19)
 - Religious (11)
 - Uncertain (7)
 - Medical (2)
 - Lexical (1)
 - More
 - + Script
 - + Dialect

Figure 4. Some filters useful to select the type and language

1.5.2 Accessibility to the datasets

The report includes a revision of some functionalities of the selected digital archives for observing the ability of the digital resources and the organization of the archaeological and textual data. Accessibility to data is the primary focal point that is prioritized here.

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Figure 6 Graph of the accessibility indicators

Access to digital resources is limited through a password after the simple registration of the user which also chooses the language of the site. In our analysis, we excluded all platforms that had closed access as we cannot search any data. However, some websites guarantee partial access. This is, for example, the case of Trismegistos, an interdisciplinary portal for the study of papyrological and epigraphical resources in the Nile Valley. Users have at their disposal a limited access to the data. Since 2020, the portal adopted a subscription model, and many functionalities (including functional search in most categories) are available only for paying institutions. Of course, the presence of passwords, moreover if subjected to payment, may limit the number of users and researchers to the resources. In the case of Trismegistos is offered an institutional subscription for full and unlimited access (staff and students) based on the IP address range(s) of the campus. Our analysis displays that only 4 sites have partial access while the others are freely accessible.

However, the authentication and authorization procedures as the request to create a user account for a repository does not imply that the site is not accessible or FAIR compliant because the accessibility is specified in such a way that a machine can automatically understand the requirements, and then either automatically execute the requirements or alert the user to the requirements.

The second aspect that may condition the accessibility of users to resources are languages used for the searches.

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Figure 7 Graph of number of languages used by web sites

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According to the graph (figure 7), 32 sites use one language. It means that the search functionalities and metadata for digital collections are available in one specific language which in the main part is English. However, 8 sites give the possibility to switch one or more languages. Only the Dutch National Museum of Antiquities is in 10 different languages including also languages that use different writing systems such as Arabic, Japanese, Chinese, and Russian. Thus, the search functions and metadata may be available in 10 different languages. Although some websites, that are included in the analysis, present more than one language not all the functions are translated: for some digital collections, while search functions and metadata are available in more languages, their objects primarily or exclusively are in one or their language. In the case of Beta Masāheft only some parts of the websites, like the description of the project, are translated in different languages such as English, Arabic, Amharic, and Tigrinya.

1.5.3 Organization of archaeological and textual data

The information about the standard such as metadata, ontologies, controlled vocabularies, and taxonomies used in these online collections is not homogeneous, depending on the published documents. Usually, the platforms that give access to data are focused on the search functionalities and description of the collections, while the documentation that describes the system and structures chosen for the management and visualization of data is generic. Rarely is it possible to easily find clear information about the schema used for the logical structure of the database.

Only for 20 digital collections, it was able to find information. Here, the graph (figure 8) shows the 20 digital collections that are organized by using ontologies and metadata standards.

Figure 8 Overview of the main Semantic Standards for structuring digital archives

The results show that the most used structures are Cidoc-CRM that serves as a base ontology for concepts needed in museum documentation and cultural heritage metadata; and Dublin Core for describing digital resources (video, images, web pages, etc.) as well as physical resources such as books or works of art. These models are often used in combination with others for better describe the resources. This is the case of The Metropolitan Museum of Art which uses: Cidoc-CRM; CRMdig that is a compatible extension of Cidoc-CRM to encode metadata about the steps and methods of production ("provenance") of digitization products and synthetic digital representations such as 2D,

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3D or even animated models created by various technologies; Nomisma (The Numismatic Description Schema) that is a codified XML schema based; and Dublin Core. ARACHNE project combines: Cidoc-CRM; METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard) that is a metadata standard for encoding descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata regarding objects within a digital library expressed using the XML schema language; MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema) that is an XML Schema for bibliographic information of particular interest to libraries; and TEI. The markup language TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) is for machine-readable texts of all types, including prose, verse, texts, transcripts of spoken-word performances, dictionaries, and manuscripts and other primary sources. TEI has been chosen for the description of seven collections that includes manuscripts and epigraphs. The limited use of TEI, applied by seven digital archives, indicates that many textual resources are not described. Some online collections give the translation and transcription of texts, but it means that texts are not readable to the machine and consequently not findable and accessible.

For Musei ID, it has been applied a Dublin Core application profile called PICO AP which includes not only the elements of the DC but also elements set of other standards and elements of metadata sets used in local contexts.

The description of data or metadata implies the use of vocabularies that provide terms adequate to represent the content. The controlled vocabularies allow not only humans but also machine to find, access, interoperate and reuse data. In our analysis, eight online collections declare to use controlled vocabularies. The lack of information or not clear documentation does not allow to confirm the use of them. The most used vocabularies are the Getty Vocabularies in particular AAT, Pleaides -a gazetteer and graph of ancient places, PeriodO -a public domain gazetteer of scholarly definitions of historical, art-historical, and archaeological periods. About historical period and ancient places, there is also Trismegistos that provides stable URIs for texts, places and period. Pleaides and Trismegistos are part of the Pelagios Commons which is a formal network of equal and independent Partners, a community of researchers, scientists and curators using Linked Data methods and tools to investigate the past. It has become over the years the most important international hub for any project related to historical geography and annotation of geographical data. For describing the images of two online collections it has been used the Iconclass classification system. Every notation in Iconclass is associated with a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) that is unique to that subject heading.

In other cases, such as the online collection of the British Museums, thesauri originally set up as an internal reference tool were defined for reflecting the nature of the collections.

In order that resources will be inside the Web and findable it is important not only to unpack the information for the machine and use shared vocabularies but also identify them with URIs and use RDF to be a linked resource that point to others. According to the graph, more than 25 projects and institutions guarantee URIs, a persistent ID, and its representation in a human-readable form using HTML.

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1.5.4 Licences

Another interesting aspect pertains to licenses. According to the graph, only 7 collections are fully protected by copyright, whereas the most frequently used license is the Creative Commons (CC), particularly CC BY. This license permits reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, as long as proper attribution is given to the creator. It also allows for commercial use while crediting the creator.

Figure 10 Licenses CC BY

Analysing the CC BY licenses, it is possible to see that 13 projects apply more conditions. Three projects indicate a CC BY-SA license which allows for commercial use. Reusers may remix, adapt, or build upon the material, but must license the modified material under identical terms; five projects establish a license CC BY-NC which defines that reusers may distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for non-commercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator.

For some collections it has been indicated a variable license, that is why the accessibility and reuse of resources depend on data type and the restrictions established by the providers. LACMA defines that some data are in the public domain, others protected by copyright; NYU has researched copyright requirements and restrictions for each of the countries of publication and believes the materials displayed on this site have been cleared by the rightsholder, are specified in the rights statement attached to each work, or are in the public domain; The University of Michigan Library provides access to the materials for educational and research purposes. However, these materials may be protected by copyright. In particular, 175.413 images/descriptions are openly available, and 49 images are restricted only descriptions are openly available. Corpus Louvre indicates that some resources are made available without restrictions according to the CC or Etalab licenses; others may be protected by copyright.

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In the case of online databases where it is not allowed the download, there is no information about terms and permissions to use data.

1.6 Some remarks

The analysis of digital collections yields intriguing insights. The first consideration concerns infrastructures which aggregate resources. Not all data providers, institutions, museums or private institutions, have the economic and technological possibility and expertise to publish data on the Web. Infrastructure can play a pivotal role by leveraging its expertise and resources to support data providers. In this context, the concept of aggregating various repositories, whether already online or in the process of going online, can be particularly appealing, especially for institutions lacking the capability to do so independently. From the user's point of view, it appears interesting because it allows the user to explore collections of digital data, mostly from museums. In the case of Egyptian artifacts scattered among disparate museums and institutions, the aggregator can facilitate public access to the resources. These infrastructures seek to standardize data-management such as the process to retrieving digital resources through a single web page dedicated to search functionalities. This is possible because aggregators propose an annotation framework according to standard methods, metadata, and taxonomies which leads to another important aspect: the need of the users to easily search for data. Standards facilitate users to retrieve data and reuse them for new applications. Of interest is the creation of APIs that guarantee access to all public data and allow developers to explore and integrate the museum public data into their projects on an ongoing way. An example is what the Art Institute Chicago has done.

One of the aspects that emerged from the analysis of these projects is the use of many standards. By downloading the XML files of the published resources, one can see that metadata, vocabularies, and thesauri depend on resource description. This means that more than one standard is used and appears in the XML file. This practice could be interesting because the application of different metadata and vocabularies can support better descriptions of concepts and properties than using only one. In the meantime, it would be interesting to motivate those choices.

The second consideration that appears most important in the light of the purpose of this survey, is the annotation of texts. In most digital archives, texts are considered only as part of the artifact that supports them. Usually, the physical object is the main subject of the annotation. For this reason, it is described by providing general information about the place of finding, place of storage, size and characteristics, while texts, most often, are not included in the annotation process except for the indication of language and type of content. From the researcher's point of view, the definition of a type and the content of the text depend on several aspects that are not based on the medium alone. Of all forty projects considered here, eight focused on the texts themselves by recording the content and noting transcripts and translations. Five of them use TEI and EpiDoc standards to index the texts. The use of controlled vocabularies and metadata is not always stated in documents about digital collections. In other cases, vocabularies are not standard but created and customized according to the needs of the project. There are projects such as the SITH Project Karnak, which collects Egyptian resources from the Karnak temple. It includes lists of Egyptian terms, ethnonyms, toponyms, anthroponyms, theonyms, and royal titles. A transcription and translation are given for each inscription. Words in the texts are linked to the term index, which provides the translation, and to all sentences in which the same word is found.

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The technology utilized for storing and sharing data is an intriguing aspect. Certain projects, such as Beta Masāheft, manage data, schema, and guidelines within a public GitHub organization, featuring several repositories accessible to project members for data utilization and contributions. The use of GitHub implies that the data is maintained independently from any particular application. Consequently, the data is not bound to a specific software or interface, and the website serves as just one potential presentation method for this data. Some repositories are synced to the server. This allows users to enter data to benefit from a fully synced research environment and thus to see the latest changes and updates to the data. Indeed, an important aspect is the possibility to easily update data moreover in the case of ancient texts, written in an ancient language where scientific upgrades, according to new research, are so important. Such a system can keep track of each change and each other's progress in the annotation of data.

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2 Appendix

Card N°1

Project name: ISAC Integrated Database Project (IDB)

Institution name: The Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures at the University of Chicago the

URL: <https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/isac-integrated-database-project-idb>

Description of the institution: The Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures comprehensive collections, including artifacts, photographs, excavation records, administrative documents, and publications, serve the public in exhibits and online, as well as being an extremely rich resource for scholars.

Contacts: isac-museum@uchicago.edu

Abstract of the project: The Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures Integrated Database Project aims to provide public access to information about the diverse research and object-based collections managed and cared for by the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures via an online Collections Search. The project began in 2005 and has involved migrating data from the older databases to an EMu (Electronic Museum) database platform. For public access to information about the collections, a public website portal was created and functional development to this "front end" will continue for the foreseeable future to provide access to more data and improve user experience. Management of the materials that comprise ISAC's collections is organized into five units: Museum Registration, Tablet Collection, Archives, Conservation, and the Research Library. Additionally, individual faculty and research projects also maintain materials such as study collections; project materials in process, such as current excavation drawings, records, and notes; and other unpublished materials which have not yet been turned over to the Institute.

Description of the database: A bundle map of the OI EMu Schema is provided at: <https://emudata.fieldmuseum.org/emu-schema-map/edgebundle-oi.html>

Data and description: The collections database contains over 1,000,000 records covering over 250,000 objects in the museum collection and exhibit galleries, over 580,000 books and articles in the Research Archives library, over 30,000 items in the Museum Archives, and over 100,000 image files from our Photo Archives.

Data model: no standards are indicated.

Output: images, pdf.

How to use data: Access to certain materials may be limited based on various factors, including but not limited to publication status, accessibility, time constraints, and the stability and fragility of the objects. All images are protected by copyright laws and, unless otherwise specified, are owned by the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures. Any publication, distribution, exhibition, or reproduction of images (in print, electronic, online, or other media) is strictly prohibited without prior written permission from the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures Museum.

Extraction of dataset: To conduct a search, the user can enter keywords into the search boxes. The results can then be narrowed down by selecting from various departments, research archives, museum collections, museum archives, and photo archives. For further refinement, it is possible to

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utilize the refine results column. Advanced search functions and filters are also available for more precise searches. Additionally, the browse museum galleries tool is available to locate records for objects currently on display in the Oriental Institute Museum. Each drop-down menu in the browse section provides additional refinement options for the records the user wishes to view. According to the aim of the deliverable, searching for "religious text(s)" yields three tabs with three lists of results: in "Archives", bibliographic references are provided ; in "Museum Collection", religious texts such as ostraca or tablets are mentioned; in "Digital Archives," objects related to the religious sphere are displayed.

Card N°2

Project name: Museo Egizio Collection Online

Institution name: Museo Egizio, Torino, Italy

URL: <https://collezioni.museoegizio.it/>

Description of institution: The Museo Egizio, the world's oldest museum exclusively dedicated to ancient Egyptian culture, was established in 1824 within the Collegio dei Nobili building, initially to showcase the Drovetti collection acquired by King Carlo Felice. Throughout the 19th century, the museum expanded and opened to the public in 1832, housing not only Egyptian artifacts but also Roman, pre-Roman, prehistoric items, and a natural history section alongside the Academy of Sciences. Notable additions included the Gallery of the Kings and acquisitions from archaeological expeditions led by Schiaparelli and Farina in Egypt, which brought around 30,000 artifacts to Turin between 1903 and 1937. Major renovations occurred in 1908 and 1924, with the latter marked by the restructuring of the Schiaparelli Wing to accommodate finds from Assiut and Gebelein. Further alterations took place in the 1930s and late 1980s, notably the installation of the Art Gallery and a new layout for the Schiaparelli Wing. A significant addition was the reconstruction of the rock temple from Ellesiya in 1970, a gesture of gratitude from Egypt for Italy's assistance in rescuing Nubian temples threatened by the Aswan dam. With rising visitor numbers from the 1980s, the museum underwent continuous updates to accommodate exhibits and improve visitor experience. This included reorganizing exhibition spaces, reclaiming underground areas for archaeological displays, and rearranging statuary for the 2006 Winter Olympics in Turin by set designer Dante Ferretti. The most recent refurbishment, completed for the grand reopening in 2015, involved extensive renovations to the museum's spaces, creating a five-floor exhibition itinerary and updated facilities to enhance the overall visitor experience.

Contacts: info@museoegizio.it

Abstract of the project: The database offers a selection of 4,700 out of approximately 40,000 items from the Egyptian Museum collection. The images are downloadable and freely reusable under the Creative Commons CCo Public Domain license.

Description of the database: not available.

Data and description: The selection of items in the database spans from the Neolithic period (5000 BC) to the Islamic period (1940 AD). Regarding the Pharaonic period, the data encompasses the 1st Dynasty through the 21st Dynasty.

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Data model: no standards are indicated.

Access to database: to access data it is necessary to select the section “Discover the museum” > “Collection and research”. No information about the database is available.

Output: A webpage presents a list of objects resulting from a search, accompanied by the total count of objects. Each entry in the list features a thumbnail, title, and catalogue number. Clicking on an object opens a new webpage dedicated to that object, which includes a carousel of images, a brief description, and detailed metadata such as inventory number, material, dimensions, date, period, dynasty, pharaoh (if applicable), provenance, acquisition details, museum location, and selected bibliography. Additionally, there is a section suggesting related searches based on metadata categories such as place, dynasty, and material. These suggestions consist of links to relevant webpages along with the number of related objects.

How to use data: it allows downloading images and reused them under Creative Commons CC BY 2.0.

Extraction of dataset: in the section “Consult dataset”, it is possible to select the language (Italian or English) and then write the words of the research. The search mask is characterized by the following metadata: Full-text search in headings, objects, Inventory number; Provenance, Period (drop down menu); CGT; Acquisition, Dynasty (drop down menu); Material (drop down menu); From year; To Year; Pharaoh (drop down menu).

It is not possible to extract easily religious texts. Searching for religious texts in the main search box the list of results contains only two records.

Card N°3

Project Name: Turin Papyrus Online Platform (TPOP)

Institution Name: Museo Egizio

URL: <https://collezionepapiri.museoegizio.it/>

Description of institution: See Card 2.

Contacts: collezione.papiri@museoegizio.it

Description of the database: The central concept of this project is the “Turin Papyrus Online Platform” (TPOP), an open-access repository. It is a multi-user platform, enabling the community of experts based at different European locations to contribute data. The language is English.

Data and description: For each resource, it is described the object as support of the texts and the text itself. Each object in TPOP has a unique number, which can be used to form a permanent link. In the Object tab is indicated the field “Other number” which includes:

- numbers written on the glass frame (such as P.N.) or labels of uncertain meaning attached to the fragments
- CGT-numbers assigned to joined papyri that also have a Cat.-number (the Cat.-number takes precedence over the CGT number)

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- numbers given in essential publications such as Gardiner, Late Egyptian Miscellanies (e.g. LEM 12) or Černý, Late Ramesside Letters (e.g. LRL 24).
- TM-numbers linked to the stable URL of <http://www.trismegistos.org>

Data model: Each object is documented with metadata about its inventory number(s), current location, physical features (including sheet joins and overlaps, measurements and material) and the conservation/restoration process, as well as the features of the text witnesses it carries (state of preservation, writing, layout, scribal practice, mode of inscription, type of text, content, keywords, date, etc.) and drawings (type, colour, grid, etc.), if any. The vocabulary for the drop-down lists for the description of the witnesses and their dating was imported from the ongoing Thot project (Thesauri & Ontology for Documenting Ancient Egyptian Resources; <http://thot.philo.ulg.ac.be>) and the Leiden Deir El-Medina Database. The open-source JSesh hieroglyph-writing software²² is integrated into the platform: the hieroglyphic text can be produced automatically from the Manuel de Codage field. Data are linked with Trismegistos.

Output: images produced as high-resolution TIFF scans at a 1:1 scale, excel file of the search results, pdf

How to use data: The user is allowed to use the images provided in the Turin Papyrus Online Database in accordance with the license Attribution Public domain CCo "No Rights Reserved". PDF files provided by cooperation partners are uploaded under the license Attribution-NonCommercial (CC BY-NC).

Extraction of dataset: there are two main masks for the search functions:

1. For non-registered users.
2. Registered users.

For non-registered users a limited number of texts are available. High resolution photographs, general description in English, and in some cases a transliteration, translation and hieroglyphs are provided for these papyri. While registered users can access over than 12000 texts. In the non-registered users mask it is possible to fill the search field with keywords or inventory number. There are drop-down windows for Text Type where it is indicated "religious text"¹, Script, Epoch, Dynasty, Pharaoh.

The mask for registered users features two options: 'Objects,' which provides a list of online resources, and 'Search.' To formulate a search query, it's crucial to specify values for each of the three search boxes.

Card N°4

Project name: MuseiD-Italia

Institution name: Italian Ministry for Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MiBACT) with the scientific consultation of the Scuola Normale Superiore of Pisa

Associated project to RESILIENCE

URL:

https://museid.culturaitalia.it/dettaglio/?language=it&case=&id=oai%3Aculturaitalia.it%3Amuseiditalia-coll_935

Description of institution: The project is promoted and managed by the Ministry for Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MiBACT) with the scientific consultation of the Scuola Normale Superiore of Pisa.

Contacts:

https://www.culturaitalia.it/opencms/museid/contatti_it.jsp?language=it&tematica=static

Abstract of the project: The project established the creation of a dedicated section within the Culturaitalia Portal for Italian museums (MuseiD-Italia), providing users access to information about museums, monuments, public and private parks, and gardens. This information encompasses details about public services, collections, and enables users to search and compare works from various collections across different institutions. Additionally, it facilitates the discovery of information related to exhibitions nationwide. The cultural data showcased on the portal is sourced directly from the entities responsible for managing these resources, both from the public administration and private companies. These operators upload only metadata, which includes descriptive information about the resources they possess. Culturaitalia offers users the ability to explore and search for information on Italian cultural resources within a single platform, enabling them to discover a wide array of resources comprising the nation's rich cultural heritage, such as museums, photographs, libraries, archives, galleries, exhibitions, monuments, videos, discs, and more. Users can utilize this platform for scientific research or simply out of curiosity.

Description of the database: the database is available through the portal and it deals with files with the information of the Italian museums and their collections.

Data and description: the digital resources are 72.540. However, only a few institutions provide available images. Each resource is described by using an ID. The identifier does not correspond to the URL

Data model: Mets, Pico, OAI

Output: the webpage MuseiD-Italia allows searching collections, monuments or objects that are part of collections. When one make a search, a list of resources is generated, giving the title and thumbnail if available. By clicking on one resource, it is possible to access to a web page where the same resource is described giving the title of the physical object, and other metadata according to the typology of the resource.

Example 1: building: the web page gives a geographical map with its position; descriptive metadata such as Type, Category, Is referenced by, Provider, Rights, General information (place and contacts of the structure, and eventually contacts for booking the visit).

Example 2: monument: the web page includes the image with licence, and metadata such as Type, Category, Author, Date of creation, Extent, Digital Object > Address₁, Relations> Is part of and Identifier, Rights.

Example 3: collection: the web page includes a carousel of images if they are available. The metadata are Type, Category, Address, Identifier, Riths, Relations> Is part of.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

At the end of each web page, there is a section with a list of similar items.

How to use data: It is allowed the download of the XML of the Pico and Mets data model.

Extraction of dataset: there is a search bar and facets. The facets are organized in Resources, Category, Type, Objects, Spatial Coverage. It is difficult to make thematic research such as resources with religious aspect. Even if the site is in Italian and English, it is possible to search only in Italian.

Card N°5

Project name: Corpus of Ptolemaic Inscriptions (CPI)

Institution name: University of Oxford

URL: <http://cpi.csad.ox.ac.uk/>

Description of the project: The project aims to create a Corpus of up-to-date editions of the Greek, bilingual and trilingual inscriptions on stone from Ptolemaic Egypt (323-30 BCE), based on material collected and annotated by the late Peter Fraser FBA (1918-2007). The Corpus consists of a publication in print in three volumes, covering Alexandria and the Delta (Volume 1), The Fayum and Middle Egypt (Volume 2) and Upper Egypt and the Oases (Volume 3). CPI appears in an online edition of texts and translations marked up in xml following EpiDoc electronic editorial conventions.

Contacts: csad@classics.ox.ac.uk

Description of database: Not available.

Data and description: The Corpus of Ptolemaic Inscriptions (CPI) consists of more than 650 Ptolemaic epigraphic monuments. The Corpus contains a range of epigraphic evidence, both Greek and Greek-Egyptian, bilingual and trilingual texts, inscribed on a wide variety of materials such as architecture, statuary, stelae and other types of stone monument and reflects almost every aspect of public and private life. Topographically, the Corpus covers the entire Ptolemaic Kingdom of Egypt, along the Nile Valley. The website displays a list of inscriptions that have a TM (Trismegistos) identifier that led to the webpage of Trismegistos with general information about the support. Only the inscriptions from the north of Egypt have a dedicated webpage with an CPI identifier. The webpage displaying inscriptions provides both the translation of the text and its corresponding image.

Data model: On the webpage, it is stated that inscriptions are encoded and marked up in XML using EpiDoc editorial conventions for online publication. This follows the format set by MAMA XI and numerous other projects like IGCyr, IRCyr, and IOSPE. The online presentation will include lemmata, texts, translations, critical notes, and brief introductory comments for each inscription. However, commentaries and extensive discussions will be reserved for the print publication. The online version will feature a broader array of images and illustrations compared to the print edition. Ahead of its scheduled online release in summer 2021, translations and images of the inscriptions in CPI volume I can be accessed through the provided links for individual texts.

Output: It is not possible to download files; users can only read the information and view the images of the resources.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

How to use data: No guidance is given regarding the usage of the data available in the database.

Extraction of dataset: Search functions are not implemented. There exist lists of inscriptions according to the geographical area where they were found.

Card N°6

Project name: Musem

Institution name: Several institutions are included into the project. The complete list is available at: <http://demo-movio-musem.gruppometa.it/en/6/Institutions>.

URL: <http://demo-movio-musem.gruppometa.it/en/1/Home>

Description of the project: Musem Collections Pilot was created within the AthenaPlus project thanks to a cooperation among different partners and it aims at showcasing museum collections with a new presentation model. The enhanced and quality metadata produced by museum curators in respect to LIDO metadata model is generated by MINT and elaborated inside MOVIO.

Contact: info@athenaplus.eu

Description of the database: Not available.

Data and description: The resources comprise over 1,000 content items from more than 20 museum institutions. They are organized according to a thesaurus navigation system, akin to Getty's AAT (Art & Architecture Thesaurus).

Data model: LIDO.

Output: It is possible to access each resource by means of the data provider's object view, and eventually download the file.

How to use data: Each record is available by means of the data provider's license.

Extraction of dataset: Data are organized in respect to a thesaurus navigation. It is possible to access data by the search function basic indicating a keyword, or the title, place, and name/person. It is possible to use filters such as object classification, object work type, and institutions. Furthermore, there is the explore function. It is possible to access this function by clicking on the menu bar. The exploration can be done by work type, by object classification, by time, by place.

Card N°7

Project name: Papyri.info

Institution name: Several institutions collaborated to the projects which aggregates material from the Advanced Papyrological Information System (APIS), Duke Databank of Documentary Papyri (DDbDP), Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis der griechischen Papyrusurkunden Ägyptens (HGV), Bibliographie Papyrologique (BP), and depends on close collaboration with Trismegistos, for rigorous maintenance of relationship mapping and unique identifiers. Work is in progress to incorporate content from the Arabic Papyrological Database (APD) as well.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

URL: <https://papyri.info/>

Description of the project: papyri.info is a data repository and publication platform that delivers the original texts of all papyri published to date together with related research data drawn from a number of resources in Germany (the Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis), Belgium (Trismegistos, the Leuven Database of Ancient Books, and the Bibliographie Papyrologique), and the United States (the Advanced Papyrological Information System). The contents are for the most part documentary papyri, pertaining to the daily life of the inhabitants of Egypt over a full millennium. Literary and sub-literary texts preserved on papyrus are currently being added via the joint German-American initiative, the Digital Corpus of Literary Papyri. A wide array of functions enables scholars to search the corpus for specific information. Translations and metadata are also provided, such as dates, provenance, information on available images.

Contact: hugh.cayless@duke.edu

Description of the database: papyri.info represents a papyrological research tool with two main functions: to access collections of non-literary texts via its Papyrological Navigator (PN) interface which supports searching, browsing, and aggregation of ancient papyrological documents and related materials, and to edit such entries and their apparatus criticus according to relevant critical editions via the Papyrological Editor (PE) which enables multi-author, version controlled, peer reviewed scholarly curation of papyrological texts, translations, commentary, scholarly metadata, institutional catalog records, bibliography, and images.

Data model: Data are organized using TEI and Epidoc. Moreover, papyri.info collaborates with Trismegistos for rigorous maintenance of relationship mapping and unique identifiers.

Output: It is possible to download metadata in XML.

How to use data: All data is available under a Creative Commons Attribution license in the idp.data repository on GitHub. The Papyrological Editor on papyri.info is powered by SoSOL.

Extraction of dataset: to access to PE is necessary the login.

Regarding the search function, it can be guided using the following parameters:

More about string-search

More about searching by Series and Collection

More about searching by Provenance

More about searching by Name

More about searching by Date

More about searching by Language

More about searching by Translation Language

More about searching by Image

However, the option to search by text type is currently unavailable.

Card N°8

Project name: PAThs (complete title: "Tracking Papyrus and Parchment Paths. An Archaeological Atlas of Coptic Literature. Literary Texts in Their Original Context. Production, Copying, Usage, Dissemination and Storage")

Institution name: Università di Roma La Sapienza, Dipartimento di Storia Antropologia Religioni Arte Spettacolo.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

URL: <http://paths.uniroma1.it> <https://atlas.paths-erc.eu/>

Description of the project: Established with an ERC grant (Advanced Grant 2015, no. 687567), primary objective of the project is to delve into a comprehensive diachronic comprehension and efficient portrayal of the geographical landscape of Coptic literary output, particularly focusing on the body of literary compositions, predominantly of religious nature, crafted in Egypt between the 3rd and 13th centuries in the Coptic language. It employs an innovative and interdisciplinary approach, integrating philology, codicology, palaeography, archaeology, archaeometry, and digital humanities, to investigate the processes of production, replication, utilization, dissemination, and preservation of Coptic works within the specific geographical contexts of their origin, encompassing both the texts themselves and the mediums on which they were inscribed.

Contacts: paola.buzi@uniroma1.it

Abstract of the project: The creation of a thorough digital Archaeological Atlas of Coptic Literature offers a fresh, all-encompassing viewpoint on the expansion and evolution of Coptic literary traditions and manuscript practices. This adaptable resource facilitates meticulous and targeted inquiries, enabling the correlation of chronological, regional, and thematic information. Moreover, it visually elucidates the interplay between archaeological findings, geographical landscapes, and the intellectual endeavors documented in manuscripts, shedding light on the dynamic relationship between settlements and literary activity.

Description of the database: The Archaeological Atlas of Coptic Literature is based on a central web database. The database is composed of seven fundamental parts (entities), dedicated to Places, Manuscripts, Works, Authors, Titles, Colophons, and Collections. Each part addresses specific issues and follows its own methodological guidelines and descriptive protocols which are closely linked to each other in a network pattern that draws its strength from these links. The principal aim is to provide the literary and manuscript tradition with a sound archaeological and geographical context and vice-versa. The schema of the database is available at: <https://github.com/paths-erc/docs/blob/master/schema/dbms.md>.

Data and description: Each manuscript or codicological unit is provided with a stable identifier, the CLM (Coptic Literary Manuscript) identifier. When the codicological units have been already classified and/or described by other projects (CMCL mainly, but also Trismegistos, LDAB, Digital Edition of Coptic Old Testament) a reference to their identifiers is always provided. When only one or a few fragments of an original codicological unit survive, these are classified per se, being temporarily considered as codicological units, until other complementary fragments have been identified and a CMCL siglum or an CLM ID has been assigned to the virtually reconstructed codex. Each manuscript is provided with a description, the place where the codicological unit has been found, and any other places of political, religious, and cultural significance, also related to the production, storage and circulation of manuscripts. Furthermore, a census, edition, and translation of Coptic titles and colophons. A classification of book formats, writing supports and other relevant codicological features of the manuscripts, in relation to the texts that they transmit.

There is an annotated list and reasoned classification of the authors related to Coptic literature.

A selected corpus of texts that were already available in electronic version are being marked-up.

Data model: the marked-up texts use TEI (Text Encoding Initiative).

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Output: it is possible to save the query.

How to use data: the license used is CC BY-NC-SA 4.0.

Extraction of dataset: The Atlas gives full access to the main database and provides different types of search experience, from the easiest (and easy to perform) to the most refined and granular. There are different web pages where to start the research: Place, People, Manuscripts, Works, Authors, Titles, Colophons, Persons, Collections. However, it is not possible to search “religious texts”.

Card N°9

Project name: Mummy Label Database

Institution name: Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Barcelona), and Universidad Complutense (Madrid).

URL: <https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/projects/mummy-label-database-mld>

Description of the project: The Mummy Label Database (MLD) is a collaborative project involving the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, the Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Barcelona), and the Universidad Complutense (Madrid). Examining roughly 2500 known and edited mummy labels poses a challenge due to their scattered publication in various periodicals and journals. This initiative aims to tackle this challenge by establishing an online database for easy access to published labels and by reissuing defective or incomplete ones. Additionally, efforts will be made to locate missing labels, especially those from private collections or lost during events such as World War II. Mummy labels, typically crafted from wood, were used to identify corpses during transportation to necropolises. Inscribed in Demotic, Greek, or occasionally hieratic or hieroglyphic scripts, they offer vital information about the deceased and sometimes contain religious invocations for the afterlife. This abstract summarizes the project's objectives and underscores the significance of mummy labels as valuable sources for understanding ancient burial practices and beliefs.

Contacts: mummylabeldb@gmail.com

Description of the database: The user can download a PDF file functioning as a guide for the use of various tabs, particularly focusing on "Bibliography," "MLDatabase," and "Links," along with the information available within them, from the website <https://deathonthenile.upf.edu/> (https://deathonthenile.upf.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/INSTRUCTIONS-MLD_o.pdf).

Data and description: Each mummy label is categorized into seven distinct fields: Catalog Information, Archaeological Information and Date, Material Description, Dimensions, Text and Translation, Publication, and Images.

Data model: TEI, Epidoc.

Output: The user can download the xml file (in TEI).

How to use data: No guidance is given regarding the usage of the data available in the database.

Extraction of dataset: There are two ways to access the information of a mummy label:

Associated project to RESILIENCE

1- Search by field/s. This option allows the user to search according to a specific field (provenance, date, material, language...) the information contained in one or more mummy labels. The user can refine the search thanks to a second pull-down menu related to the first field of search.

2- Search through the keyboard. This tool allows the user to search for a specific Greek/Demotic word contained in the text of a mummy label.

Card N°10

Project name: Corpus Louvre

Institution name: Musée du Louvre

URL: <https://corpus.louvre.fr/s/corpus/page/accueil>

Abstract of the project: Corpus Louvre is a digital gateway providing access to sources and research data generated at the Louvre Museum on its collections. The platform offers and enables simultaneous access to documentary and scientific resources shedding light on the history, understanding, and transmission of the collections. The portal is only in French.

Contacts: There is no contact address provided for any inquiries.

Description of the database: A description of the database is not available. However, at the webpage <https://corpus.louvre.fr/s/corpus/page/a-propos>, the offerings of Corpus are outlined.

Data and description: Data include digitized documents (such as old photographic collections, private archive collections, etc.) sourced from the museum's conservation department documentations and organized into collections. Additionally, databases derived from research conducted by the museum's scientific teams and their partners are presented in the form of thematic websites. Corpus categorizes resources into three thematic areas corresponding to major research domains at the Louvre Museum: 1) Museum Studies - History of Collections; 2) Artwork Studies; 3) Material and Technique Studies.

Data model: CIDOC-CRM

Output: Results of a search can be exported in CSV format, and the website also provides the option to harvest notice texts in structured JSON format. The images available in Corpus can be accessed through the IIF Mirador viewer.

How to use data: No guidance is given regarding the usage of the data available in the database.

Extraction of dataset: Users have access to all Corpus resources through various search and exploration tools, including a full-text search engine, advanced search form, and facets for filtering search results. The site shows data that have an inventory number (such as fonds of ancient photographs, private archives etc.) and come from the departments of conservation of the museum and are organized in collections. Others consist of databases of the research groups of the museum. It is possible to access to resources by using the search engine, the advanced research and filters.

Card N°11

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Project name: Ancient World Digital Library (AWDL)

Institution name: New York University, Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW)

URL: <http://dlib.nyu.edu/ancientworld/>

Description of the project: The Ancient World Digital Library (AWDL) is an initiative of the Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW) at New York University. AWDL is a publicly available digital library of public domain content on the ancient world. AWDL currently provides digital access to over 400 volumes across subjects such as Egyptology, Assyriology, Papyrology, and Classical Antiquity.

Contacts: david.ratzan@nyu.edu, ISAW-library@nyu.edu

Abstract of the project: The Ancient World Digital Library (AWDL) identifies, collects, curates, preserves, and provides access to a broad range of scholarly materials relevant to the study of the ancient world. It provides a digital platform for small presses, scholarly societies, and other independent publishers that are interested in digitizing and publishing their scholarship online for a wider scholarly audience. The target audience includes academic researchers, students, librarians, and the interested public.

Description of database: not available

Data and description: data consists of works visualized by using IIIF. The Collection Overview section includes 10 distinct collections: Ancient Judaism, Central Asia, Egyptology, Papirology, Ancient Science, Classical Antiquity, Hittitology, Assyriology, Early Christianity, and Iranian Studies. By choosing one of these collections, users can access, and view works related to the respective discipline. AWDL's digitization efforts were focused on materials that fit the following criteria: 1) Items within the collecting scope of the ISAW Library, as described at <https://isaw.nyu.edu/library/About/collection-guidelines>; 2) Items for which we can identify the rightsholder (either individual or institutional) and negotiate permissions for online publication; 3) Items that are not freely available through other digital library projects.

Data model: AWDL supports multiple standards depending on the nature of the work. The records that ISAW produces conform to a flat, idiosyncratic data model informed by the DCMI Metadata Terms and the Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) It uses KBART-metadata. KBART ("Knowledge Bases and Related Tools") is a NISO Recommended Practice that facilitates the transfer of holdings metadata from content providers to knowledge base suppliers and libraries. Knowledge bases are widely used to support library link resolvers and electronic resource management systems. Metadata records for AWDL content are published periodically for the public at: <https://github.com/NYULibraries/kbart-metadata>.

Output: it is possible to download the pdf of works.

How to use data: NYU has researched copyright requirements and restrictions for each of the countries of publication and believes the materials displayed on this site have been cleared by the rightsholder, are specified in the rights statement attached to each work, or are in the public domain.

Extraction of dataset: data can be extracted with the search engine or filters.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Project name: iDAI.objects arachne

Institution name: German Archaeological Institute (DAI) and the Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory (CoDArchLab) at the University of Cologne.

URL: <https://arachne.dainst.org/>

Description of the project: iDAI.objects arachne (short form: Arachne) is the central object-database of the German Archaeological Institute (DAI) and the Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory (CoDArchLab) at the University of Cologne. Intended as an internet research tool for the Archaeologies and experts of ancient studies, it offers a means to access objects and their states and to search efficiently in hundreds of thousands of datasets. Arachne feeds from analogue and digital sources. By employing Semantic Web strategies, Arachne provides a low-threshold structure for these data. All digitized images and textual data in Arachne are preserved for the long term and available online.

Contacts: not available.

Abstract of the project: The principles of open access and open source are combined with the openness for cooperation on which iDAI.world is based. The iDAI.world is a digital research environment based on tools and repositories that enable researchers to collect, analyze, visualize, publish and store research data and creative output. It supports research and scholarly communication in archaeology and related academic fields with digital tools for documentation, normative data and analysis tools. Systems for digital publication and long-term archiving complete the spectrum. Multilingualism and worldwide access are guiding principles of iDAI.world. The name Arachne refers to the database itself as well as the system for displaying the data. The database is based on MariaDB, a free fork of MySQL. The long-term preservation of all object information in the database is guaranteed by a Tivoli Storage System with multiple redundancies. In the last version "Arachne 3" the user interface was based on PHP / JavaScript and Apache with solr for indexing the data. The current version "Arachne 4" introduced a conceptual separation between the frontend in the user's internet browser and the backend acting as the intermediary between the frontend and the database. The frontend is an AngularJS application, the backend is programmed in Java with Elasticsearch instead of solr for indexing.

Description of the database: The Arachne database is a central subsystem of the iDAI.welt, the software architecture of the German Archaeological Institute, consisting of various interconnected modules and oriented in their data on open access and in its programming to open source. The modules of the iDAI.welt (e.g. iDAI.objects, iDAI.field, iDAI.gazetteer) are in a constant process of development by new technological and scientific methods and possibilities. Interoperability is becoming increasingly important, especially between Arachne as an image and object database and the various geographical information systems (GIS), used on excavations and surveys, to combine different categories of data while keeping redundant data as low as possible. Another central issue is the provision of URIs (Universal Resource Identifier) for all objects digitally captured. The integration of the CIDOC-CRM and the Open Archives Initiative into iDAI.objects is of great importance.

iDAI.archives is based on ATOM, iDAI.bibliography on Koha, iDAI.thesauri is based on iQvoc and iDAI.geoserver is based on the open geoserver software-stack of the Open-Source Geospatial Foundation. Other iDAI.world systems are being developed in house, like the excavation database

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iDAI.field, but all the code of the DAI is being shared and published in the GitHub repository. No proprietary software is used inside of the iDAI.world.

Data and description: The database contains 4,723,913 entries, including: over 2.9 million images and 600 3D models, over 350,000 contextualized objects with: approx. 975,000 location references, approx. 160,000 dating information and approx. 275,000 bibliographic references as well as 23,226 books with a total of over 1.1 million book pages.

Data model: Arachne follows a paradigm of highly structured object-metadata which is mapped onto the CIDOC-CRM, to address machine-readable metadata strategies of the Semantic Web. This requires high efforts in time and money and therefore is only possible for privileged areas of data. While on the ever-increasing range of new, digital born data in reality only a small effort-per-object ratio can be applied. It therefore requires a "low-threshold" processing structure that is located in the »unstructured world« of Arachne.

In order to guarantee the highest data interoperability, the Arachne database provides its data in several metadata formats delivered through different application interfaces. The METS profile constitutes the container format which represents the structure of a document and can comprise its bibliographic metadata. The DFG Viewer uses the MODS or TEI format to display the bibliographic metadata. It can be integrated into the METS file seamlessly and can also be supplemented with further data formats there. The METS-file may contain a reference to search in fulltext via SRU. The DFG-Viewer will search, retrieve and present the results.

Output: Arachne is provided free of charge. Creating an account is optional but recommended: images will be displayed at a higher resolution. In addition, you can create object catalogues and annotate the Arachne data. Arachne will be displayed in your preferred language, if possible, with English as the default language. Since you see this text in English, your browser preference is either set to English or to another language for which no translation of this page exists at this time. Arachne uses the text encoding "Unicode (UTF-8)". Your browser should recognize this encoding automatically.

How to use data: The site is licensed under a Creative Commons License (BY-NC-ND 3.0). Contents that cannot be accessed directly in Arachne (e.g. high-resolution printable scans) are subject to different regulations, i.e. the Creative Commons License does not apply.

Extraction of dataset: The search is designed to start with one or more keywords. Searching provides a list of the datasets corresponding to the keyword selected. This list can be further filtered by using the facets. The photographic material is made available exclusively for scientific purposes and research.

Searching religious texts in the main search box, the system provides only 9 results which consist of pages of books where the word religious appears. In order to extract resources that are compliant with WP10 research, it is necessary to type different keywords which indicate the culture such as "egyptian" or "ägyptisch" and filter the results.

Card N°13

Project name: SITH: projet Karnak

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Institution name: CNRS - Labex ARCHIMEDE, ANR-11-LABX-0032-01, Programme « Investissement d'Avenir », USR 3172 - CFEETK / UMR 5140, Équipe ENiM

URL: <http://sith.huma-num.fr/karnak>

Description of the project: Initiated in January 2013, the Karnak project aims to organize and make available textual documentation from the temples of Karnak.

Contacts: sebastien.biston-moulin@cnrs.fr (Director of the project)

Abstract of the project: The work is based on a comprehensive inventory of documents and inscriptions from Karnak collated in the field.

Description of the database: A tool called "Système d'Indexation des Textes Hiéroglyphiques", is used for indexing hieroglyphic, hieratic and demotic texts. This programme is designed to create lists of words, theonyms, toponyms, ethnic names and cult places, anthroponyms and names of kings from the contents of the corpus. On the website, the section "Location of the inscriptions" lists parts of the structures which allow to access to the files with a number of objects/inscriptions that were found there. In the section chronological exploration there is a list of Dynasties and name of rulers who the inscriptions in the database were dated to. Each document is transliterated and translated with a bibliography at the end. In the section "Vocabulary" there is a list of words that are used in the texts. Everyone includes a reference to the inscriptions where it is used.

There is the possibility to create a free user account. A user account allows to view all the indexed attestations while the consultation without user account limits you to 10 results per element. A user account also allows to post comments to the project team on the various documents included in the project and, if necessary, allows to participate in the document checking and validation process before publication online.

Data and description: 7714 entries (last consultation 14/02/023) which include monuments, objects, scenes or inscriptions. They consist of images, pdf and texts. Each document is given a unique identifier number (KIU: Karnak Identifiant Unique) after its integration in the database. All the information associated with a particular document or inscription (KIU) will be accessible from a single entry.

Data model: not available

Output: images are displayed. All the photographs are stored and distributed via a system ensuring their long-term preservation. All of the textual data will be released in Open Access under a Creative Commons license (CC-BY-SA 4.0).

How to use data: No guidance is given regarding the usage of the data available in the database.

Extraction of dataset: Within the project, several indexes provide access to the content of the edited inscriptions (vocabulary, elements of royal titulatures, toponyms, ethnic and places of worship, theonyms, anthroponyms).

Card N°14

Project name: The Arnold Meijer Archives of Egyptian Art

Associated project to RESILIENCE

URL: <https://www.arnoldmeijer.nl/index.html>

Description of the project: The archives aim to facilitate the academic and private study of Egyptian Antiquities, providing an overview of objects from the art market as well as from selected literature and museum collections. Most of the art market entries are assembled from the important auction houses. The majority are from the period 1980 to the present; roughly the last four decennia.

Contacts: not available.

Abstract of the project: The archives mainly contain objects that travel between private collections and otherwise remained unpublished. As a result, it is challenging to study these objects and it is hoped that these archives can contribute to this, although they do not pretend to be complete.

Objects being included does not necessarily imply authenticity. Among the pieces on the free market there are undoubtedly also recent imitations that have not been recognized as such. Also, the dating provided may be erroneous. The files from the art market refer to their source and the publication date if applicable.

Description of the database: The database has a hierarchical structure characterized by three main nodes or folders "Stone Vessels" composed by 1448 objects, "Sculpture"1655 objects, "Figurative Amulets"1048 objects. Each folder contains other folders.

Data and description: Data consists of jpg of the pages of catalogues.

Data model: not available.

Output: All files can be downloaded free of charge.

How to use data: No guidance is given regarding the usage of the data available in the database.

Extraction of dataset: To extract data, it is necessary to open the folders.

Card N°15

Project name: DASI (Digital Archive for the Study of pre-islamic arabian Inscriptions)

Institution name: University of Pisa, Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa, CNR

URL: <http://dasi.cnr.it/>

Description of the institutions: DASI project was funded by the European Community within the Seventh Framework Programme "Ideas", through an ERC – Advanced Grant awarded to Prof. Alessandra Avanzini at the University of Pisa (2011-2016). The Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa, additional participant of the project, was responsible for the technical development of the archive, which is now maintained at the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale.

Contacts: irene.rossi@cnr.it (Scientific coordinator)

Abstract of the project: DASI seeks to gather all known pre-Islamic Arabian epigraphic material into a comprehensive online database, with the aim to make available to specialists and to the broader public a wide array of documents often underestimated because of their difficulty of access, so that

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the rich cultural heritage of ancient Arabia can be studied in a holistic manner to fill an important gap in the history of the ancient Near East. During the DASI ERC project, the University of Pisa team under the direction of Alessandra Avanzini made nearly 8,200 Ancient South Arabian inscriptions and 600 more anepigraphic objects openly accessible. The digitization of the Ancient South Arabian corpus has continued after the end of the funded project and is currently conducted at the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche.

Thanks to the collaboration with other major European centres for the study of the Arabian Peninsula, during the course of the ERC funded project, also parts of the corpora of the Ancient North Arabian inscriptions (supervision by M.C.A. Macdonald, University of Oxford), Nabataean inscriptions (supervision by Laila Nehmé, UMR 8167, CNRS-Paris) and other Aramaic inscriptions (supervision by Maria Gorea, Université de Paris VIII) were digitized. For further information regarding each corpus, please visit the corresponding sections of the archive from the Projects menu.

Description of the database: The digitization of pre-Islamic Arabian inscriptions is carried out through a data entry system that ensures standardized and secure cataloging, archiving, and indexing of data. This data is gathered in a relational database, with the inscription as the central entity, connected to other entities that provide additional description (such as information about the text's support, translation, bibliography, geographical details about the site, and visual material). There are three types of cards: epigraph card, object card, and site card. Each inscription is linked to an object – the physical material on which it was inscribed. An epigraph card can be linked, via the object card, to one or more site cards, depending on the origin and provenance of the inscription.

Data and description: Epigraphic texts are transliterated according to the Unicode Standard and encoded using a standard XML language (TEI/Epidoc), in order to annotate information concerning the structure and the onomastics of the text, and editorial interventions. A Lexicon tool has been implemented for the lexicographic study of the ASA languages, which is currently in progress. The Corpus of South Arabian Inscriptions in DASI contributed data to Trismegistos.

Data model: TEI/Epidoc. A vocabulary has been developed for describing epigraphies, support types, and decorations. Comprehensive iconographic indices have also been created. Geonames have been utilized in certain instances. The DASI data model has been aligned with the DC elements set, as mandated by the OAI-PMH protocol, and with the EDM to enable the exposure of records to the Europeana aggregation service, in addition to the mentioned EpiDoc subset.

Output: it is not possible to download any file but just read information

How to use data: Materials on the website are protected by laws of copyright and intellectual property. Some of these contents are intellectual property of the University of Pisa. Others are property of third parties that have authorized their publication. People interested in using the contents of the University of Pisa may contact via email and ask for the conditions of use.

Extraction of dataset: By entering each of the sections of the archive, the user is able to access their content by different Indexes, whose lists can be refined by using filters. Corpora of inscriptions are hierarchically organized by language and script typology; Collections of objects are organized by deposit and gather epigraphic and an-epigraphic objects from ASA collections worldwide, digitized on DASI thanks to specific agreements with museum institutions. The indexes of Epigraphs, Objects and Sites provide refinable alphabetical lists of inscription/object sigla and modern toponyms respectively, giving access to their records. Each record displays meta-information specific to its

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category, plus links to the related records; the Epigraph records also host the transcription of the inscriptional text and potential translations. A Bibliography index is also provided.

Thanks to the xml mark-up of the textual features and to the record of extra-textual features, the DASI user can enjoy two useful sections for the consultation and study of inscriptions. The Word lists allows to retrieve the list of the words occurring in the inscriptions of the archive, both for lexicon and onomastics. Two separate lists are provided: the General word list and the list of all the words with Lacunae at beginning. The Textual search tool allows to perform dynamic searches on words or patterns of words within the texts of the inscriptions. Searches can be refined using one or more filters that will be applied to the meta-information of the epigraphs or to the encoded texts. A Map is also available in the Tools section: it displays the location of the sites, whose coordinates have been recorded in the archive, and gives access to the Site cards.

Card N°16

Project name: Egyptology Books and Articles in pdf online

URL: http://egyptologyresources.x10host.com/er/bibliography/bibliography_data.html

Description of the project: The project aims to collect as many books and articles as possible on Egyptological subjects which are freely accessible to anyone without the need for privileged access. Thus, sites such as the Internet Archive, the University of Heidelberg Library, the Oriental Institute, the Metropolitan Museum, the Giza Library, Ancient World Online (AWOL), and many more were searched, as well as attempting to collect links noted in the pages of EEF (Egyptologists' Electronic Forum) News.

Contacts: not available.

Description of the database: it is not a database but a html page.

Data and description: 8149 records (Website consulted on 14/02/2023), consisting of links to webpages and to PDF files.

Data model: html page.

Output: pdf files.

How to use data: Sites that require institutional access or a password are not included—thus journals only available on JSTOR and papers available on www.academia.edu are included.

Extraction of dataset: it is possible only to scroll by author's name, titles and download the pdf file of the books.

Card N°17

Project name: Propylaeum

Institution name: Heidelberg University Library, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek in Munich.

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URL: <https://www.propylaeum.de/en/subjects/reception-of-antiquity-in-a-semantic-network-digital-books-images-and-objects/research>

Description of the project: Propylaeum is the “Specialized Information Service Classics” (FID) provided by the Heidelberg University Library and the Bayerische Staatsbibliothek in Munich. It is closely aligned with the scientific needs of the researchers. The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) supports the development of services “search technology”, “electronic publishing / Open Access”, “retro digitization and online presentation of research related media” as well as “science communication”. Bayerische Staatsbibliothek München is responsible for the fields of Byzantine Studies, Ancient History, Ancient Near Eastern Studies, Classical philology, Medieval and Neo-Latin philology and Pre- and Early History, while Heidelberg University Library is in charge of Egyptology and Classical Archeology.

Contacts: Effinger@ub.uni-heidelberg.de, Dr. Maria Effinger (Project coordinator)

Abstract of the project: PropylaeumSEARCH is the central research portal of Propylaeum. It offers simultaneous search of subject bibliographies, special subject sections of relevant library catalogues and full text sources. These databases primarily contain scientific publications on Ancient Studies. In addition, PropylaeumSEARCH includes special research possibilities of portals incorporated in Propylaeum, like Gnomon Bibliographic Database, recensio.antiquitatis or the online resources catalogued in KIRKE WebGuide Ancient Studies. The project focuses on:

1. Provision of information resources
2. Expansion of the field specific information infrastructure Propylaeum / PropylaeumSEARCH
3. Electronic publishing in Open Access – Propylaeum-E-Publishing, including extension of the offer for the project "Publishing-Plus"
4. Sustainability for excellent specialised information (Migration of the Gnomon Bibliographic Database)
5. Linked Open Data – "Digital Classics"
6. Science communication/PR/marketing

Description of the database: The software WissKI, developed with funding from the DFG and based on the content management system DRUPAL, is used. WissKI (Wissenschaftliche Kommunikationsinfrastruktur - Scientific Communication Infrastructure) is a virtual research environment and linked open data management software. Beneath the fundamental possibilities to create, read, edit and delete content, WissKI offers solutions for all tasks of the research data lifecycle and help users to produce and publish FAIR data.

Data and description: Not available.

Data model: Data are formalized using standards: CIDOC-CRM; GND, Getty Thesauri, (<https://www.propylaeum.de/en/publishing/dynamic-publishing>). It offers the possibility to digitally edit historical text and image corpora including personalized annotations and commenting features using current standard text and image labelling (XML/TEI).

Output: it is possible to download the pdf or the RDF/XML

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How to use data: Propylaeum supports Open Access as a publication model for circulating research results. It publishes both initial/primary versions of documents (“golden path”) and well secondary/re-published documents (“green path”). These publications are archived permanently and citable by standardized addresses (URN, DOI) and metadata. These identifiers can be found in library catalogues, and via Internet search engines, the world over.

For general use of PropylaeumSEARCH there is no registration necessary. Most services are available without login. But registration gives the access to additional services like saving search results in a list. To be able to use licensed data sources the researcher has to be affiliated with certain institutions like libraries or universities. Therefore, registration is mandatory for access to those databases and full text collections. They are marked by a “blocked” symbol .

Extraction of dataset: it is possible to extract data using the services such as PropyleumSEARCH. It allows to insert keywords and/or use the filters. The filters are organized in type: data Source/Institution; Author; Language; Media Type; Year and Subject. The Subject includes the filter “Religion” with 23.115 resources and “Religious aspects” with 18.680 resources.

Card N°18

Project name: Kelsey Museum Artifacts Database

Institution name: University of Michigan

URL: <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/cgi/i/image/image-idx?c=kelsey;page=index;sid=6febc1qk55vk7wjgzg3pmxlh59rv5dlgewd9jem5nrt4w;g=um-i>

Description of project: The Kelsey Museum of Archaeology Art & Artifact Collection represents the art and archaeological artifacts of the ancient Mediterranean world and its supporting archival collection, held at the Kelsey Museum at the University of Michigan.

Contacts: kelseymuse@umich.edu

Description of database: Three databases are available :

- Kelsey Museum Artifacts Database (for records of all items in the Kelsey collections)
- Michigan Excavations Records (for all records of Karanis and Seleucia excavations)
- Photo Captions database (for captions to photographs in the Kelsey Photographic Archive, excluding fine arts photographs)

Data and description: Data are divided in Numismatic, Artifacts, Photos, Ceramics, Textile, Inscriptions, Ebot/zoo, Osteology. 175.372 images/descriptions are openly available, while 49 images are restricted, and the descriptions are openly available. The database includes 83.857 items about Egypt. The metadata describe the physical object, the collection, technical details and right permission. Some Data as those from Egypt are present in the University Michigan Library Image Collections, so there is a landing page to the UM web page. Here the images can be downloaded. Moreover, they are described using IIIF

Data model: no standard declared.

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Output: It is allowed the download for 175.372 images (jpg) and descriptions.

How to use data: The University of Michigan Library provides access to these materials for educational and research purposes. These materials may be protected by copyright. If you decide to use any of these materials, you are responsible for making your own legal assessment and securing any necessary permission. If you have questions about the collection, please contact the Kelsey Museum of Archaeology. If you have concerns about the inclusion of an item in this collection, please contact Library Information Technology

Most images can be downloaded at a variety of sizes, including the full resolution if you have sufficient access. The download menu lists sizes by width x height.

Extraction of dataset: it is possible to search across all record fields or use the control to select a more specific field. The advanced search interface allows to create both simple and complex queries. It is possible to search using only one field, or connect different kinds of search terms using Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT). Each item on the results list is linked to the image entry, where one can view a larger version of the image and full descriptive information.

- the image viewer (typically)
- the actions toolbar
- record metadata
- technical metadata
- rights and premissions
- related links
- information on how to cite this item

With the image viewer, one can zoom in/out on the image (use the +/- icons) and/or move around in the image by clicking and dragging.

According to the aim of the WP10, it is possible to extract religious texts by using the filters. Once selected the category of Inscriptions, it is possible to refine the search by using the class religious inscriptions. Otherwise, there is the possibility to indicate the culture of interest like "egyptian", or the place.

Card N° 19

Project name: Munich Digital Research Archives (MUDIRA)

Institutions name: Institute of Egyptology at the University of Munich (LMU) and the State Museum of Egyptian Art Munich (SMÄK)

URL: <https://mudira.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/>

Description of the project: Mudira is a project launched in spring 2012 by the Institute of Egyptology at the University of Munich (LMU) and the State Museum of Egyptian Art Munich (SMÄK) with the aims to facilitate access to the images, scientifically process the associated information, and

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ultimately preserve the often scientifically significant representations on a contemporary storage tool.

Contacts: Not available.

Abstract of the project: Primary aim is to digitize the extensive image collections of both institutions on Ancient Egypt. In the meantime, a considerable number of additional sets of images were added, which were made available to the database by colleagues and other institutions.

Description of database: The database, created by the LMU Humanities IT Group (ITG), contains digital copies of the collections with their metadata.

Data and description: 22,000 records are included in the database, among which 35mm slides from the Egyptological Institute of the LMU Munich, approx. 3,600 images from the SMÄK, almost 6,000 images from UNI DIA Verlag, almost 5,000 pictures by Prof. Dr. Dietrich Klemm and Rosemarie Klemm, M.A., Munich, on their research on ancient Egyptian quarries and gold mining in ancient Egypt and Nubia. Approximately 770 images from the Museums in the Nile Delta project. Each data record contains an image ID as a unique identifier and names the contact person for copyright.

Data model: the general metadata give the title, location of physical object, classification, dating, description, literature, institution, photographer, legal contacts, and image id. No information about metadata standards is present on the website

Output: Images and cards could be freely consulted. Downloading images is limited to registered users.

How to use data: Even users who are not logged in have access to all data sets and can use all search functions without restriction. Downloading images is limited to registered users. Temporary user accounts or guest access cannot be enabled for copyright reasons. Any use of the images (be it through printing, reproduction, reproduction in electronic media or the like) is only possible with the prior written consent of the respective rights holder and is usually subject to a fee.

Extraction of dataset: Navigation within the Mudira image database takes place via the tabs Database and New query. Under the Database tab you will find the database search mask, in which you can search for one or a combination of the categories. By clicking on the symbol = you can switch between [is the same] and [is not the same] (example Material=Limestone for all objects made of limestone, Material≠Limestone for all objects except those made of limestone). The search operator [and] exists exclusively between the individual search fields of the search mask. To link two terms from the same database field, the corresponding field must be selected twice as a search field. With | Two search terms can be linked in the same field with [or] (example location=TT 1|TT 2 finds all images of the Theban tombs TT 1 or TT 2). As you type, indexes are displayed in the form of a suggestion list (all terms with a first letter), which opens as soon as a character has been entered into a search field. The displayed entries can be adopted as search terms with a mouse click. If further subdivisions of a search term are available as a tree structure, these are indicated by a small arrow on the right edge of the search field. The arrows open additional windows with corresponding subcategories.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Project name: Project Coptos**Institution name:** Université Lumière Lyon 2, HiSoMA UMR-5189 (CNRS-Universités de Lyon), Institut français d'archéologie orientale (IFAO), Musée des Beaux-Arts de Lyon, fonds Khéops pour l'archéologie.**URL:** <https://coptos.mom.fr/>**Description of the project:** The database was created in 2011 to catalogue artifacts from the archaeological site of Coptos, aiming to contextualize the monuments and artifacts unearthed by the French Mission of Coptos. Its goal was to quickly gather and provide access to a diverse range of materials for the excavation team. The richness of the materials and the extensive investigative work required prompted the decision to publish the collation online, aiming to share research efforts and make them widely accessible. This initiative aligns with current trends in digital humanities, addressing the gathering of dispersed heritage. The project benefited from collaborations with museums possessing significant Coptic collections, and ongoing bibliographic reviews are enhancing the database's content.**Contacts:** Laure Pantalacci Laure.Pantalacci@mom.fr (Director of French Mission of the Coptos excavations); Content of the database: Vanessa Desclaux vanessadesclaux@hotmail.com (Responsible of the content of the database); Hélène Jamet Helene.Jamet@mom.fr (IT Responsible).**Description of the database:** The database consists of a table with the following metadata: ID, title, type, material, place of conservation, inventory number, period.**Data and description:** 1793 records are available organized in a table.**Data model:** Not available.**Output:** It is possible to download jpg.**How to use data:** The textual data available in the database can be used under the Creative Commons CC-BY-SA conditions. Each object is referenced by a unique identifier (ID) to be used for any citation. The URL of each object is recalled at the bottom of each page. For images and illustrations, one should contact the institution or author of the photo mentioned in the license and sources fields. The database only publishes visuals for which reuse is permitted or for which it has obtained the right to distribute. Non-public data is accessible in connected mode to mission members and partners.**Extraction of dataset:** to extract data from the database it is possible to insert keywords in the search box, or use the filters like: ID, type (drop down menu), description, material (drop down menu), period. In order to extract religious texts, it is possible to indicate the type of object such as "stele". However, there are information about the object not about the texts.

Card N°21

Project name: Penn museum. Online Collections**Institution name:** Penn Museum, University of Pennsylvania**URL:** <https://www.penn.museum/collections/>

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Description of the institution: Penn Museum, formerly known as The University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, is an Archaeology and Anthropology Museum at the University of Pennsylvania.

Contacts: digitalmedia@pennmuseum.org; online.collections@pennmuseum.org

Abstract of the project: The database contains records for artifacts and archival films from Penn Museum, University of Pennsylvania.

Description of the database: The museum began using a customized version of KE Software's EMu (Electronic Museum) system in November 2010 to record object details and to track activities such as exhibitions, loans, and acquisitions. The new software is helping improve how objects are described, providing more detailed information both to staff and to online users. International language support in EMu, for example, is making it possible for many of the written inscriptions on objects to be entered in their native script as well as in English translation. Even some of the basic descriptors such as dates and measurements are being refined as a result of options made available in the new database and as part of ongoing efforts to provide clear, useful details online about the Museum's Collection.

Data and description: 300,000 records are available in the database. These records describe cultural and historical items. Since the 1980s a core component of the Penn Museum's various collections management systems has been a hierarchical controlled vocabulary, in Questor Systems's Argus it was called the Lexicon, in KE Software's EMu, it is called the Thesaurus but in both cases, it is a set terms organized into a hierarchy that facilitates object cataloging and searching within the collections management system. The Penn Museum's thesaurus contains approximately 67,000 terms and controls the data entered in fields like Object Name, Provenience, Material, Culture, Technique, Maker, Culture Area, Subject, and Function. The content and structure of the thesaurus allow curators, collections managers and museum staff to catalog an object with a Provenience and then be able to find that object by searching for another word because of the hierarchical relationship between the terms. ("Collection Notes- The Museum's Online Searchable Database." Expedition Magazine 53, no. 3, December, 2011, Accessed October 11, 2023. <https://www.penn.museum/sites/expedition/collection-notes-the-museums-online-searchable-database/>)

Data model: Not available.

Output: It is possible to download the object data available in the online collection as either a CSV, XML or JSON file. Each sections' data is available below as well as a single file containing all 379,498 object records. This data is provided 'as-is' (<https://www.penn.museum/collections/data.php>)-

The files contain metadata about the objects in the collection. This usually includes information about what the object is, a brief physical description, dates, where it is from and what it is made of. Some records will have more information than others. As a work in progress, the Museum continuously strives to improve both the quantity and quality of the data contained within the online database. Some fields contain multiple values (e.g. Place Name, Material and Other Number). In the CSV file, multiple values in these fields are separated by a single pipe-bar character '|'

How to use data: The Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported (CC BY 3.0) license applies to all downloaded datasets. Images are not included.

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Extraction of dataset: It is possible to use the keyword search or advanced search. There are some facets such as: Record type, Has image, On display, Section, Video categories, 3D model, Object name, Place name, Site, Period, Culture, Culture Area, Locus, Iconography, Inscription Language, Material, Technique, Maker, Bibliographic Reference Kind. In order to select religious texts from the Nile Valley the best way is to use the filters. Selecting "All Records", one can apply the filter Record type, indicating Object, and then select Inscription language for having a first list of results. This list after need to be filtered for identifying the objects and texts with religious value.

Card N°22

Project name: Database of Medieval Nubian Texts

Institution name: Chair of Epigraphy and Papyrology Faculty of Archaeology University of Warsaw, Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology University of Warsaw.

URL: <https://www.dbmnt.uw.edu.pl/>

Description of the project: The DBMNT was officially inaugurated in 2011 as an integral part of the book of Grzegorz Ochała entitled Chronological Systems of Christian Nubia, where different aspects of counting time in the Nubian kingdoms of Nobadia, Makuria, and Alwa between the mid-sixth and fifteenth centuries are treated in detail.

Contacts: g.ochala@uw.edu.pl

Abstract of the project: Aim of the project is to make available written sources of various forms and functions (from important administrative inscriptions and documents, through literary and liturgical manuscripts, private correspondence, elaborate epitaphs and modest tombstones, graffiti left by pious pilgrims on walls of churches, to various symbols scratched on ceramic vessels), executed on all possible kinds of media (stone, papyrus, paper, parchment, leather, pottery, wood, metal, textiles, glass, rocks, and walls of buildings).

The task of gathering all these sources and processing them was not easy and required browsing through an enormous quantity of publications, not infrequently extremely hard to access. As a result, along with texts that were published *lege artis* (i.e. with a full description, transcription, translation, commentary, and – most ideally – photo and/or tracing), the DBMNT includes also those that were quasi-published (i.e. they have more or less decent transcriptions but no translations and commentaries or vice versa) and those that are classified as unpublished (i.e. they are only mentioned in passing, their content is described without giving a transcription, or they are available only in the form of photographs or tracings/drawings). Of course, the last two cases are the most problematic in terms of metadata (findspot, material, technique of execution, dimensions, colour) and the user will frequently come across empty fields and fields with the note 'not recorded'. These voids will hopefully be filled in, when access to objects and/or their documentation is obtained, and new publications come out.

Description of the database: In 2011, the database consisted of 733 records, gathering all Nubian texts in which various chronological phenomena are recorded. However, since the beginning of work, the DBMNT was constructed to include different kinds of written sources from Christian Nubia, not only those containing dates and/or other chronological indicators. At present the database contains

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2942 records, which cover all possible forms of written expression left by the inhabitants of the Middle Nile Valley in the Middle Ages. The text cards are arranged in six tabs.

- 'Main card' – this includes basic information about the circumstances of discovery and present whereabouts of the text, its typological classification according to the medium on which it was executed, technique of execution, type of text, its language, contents, and date;
- 'Technical data' – here all 'material' aspects of texts are described, such as dimensions and colours of both objects and texts executed on them, number of lines, height of letters, descriptions of decorative elements and state of preservation;
- 'Chronology' – in this tab are included all pieces of information about counting time that are preserved in a given source: list of employed chronological systems, transcription and translation of dating formulae, and, extracted from them, transcriptions of names of months, weekdays, and feasts occurring in the text;
- 'Other' – here the user will find lists of personal names, toponyms/ethnonyms, and offices/titles occurring in a given text;
- 'Bibliography' – this tab is divided into four fields: 'Editio princeps', 'Latest edition', 'Other editions', and 'Other publications'. All references are given according to the system employed in G. Ochała & G. R. Ruffini, *A Guide to the Texts of Medieval Nubia*, available at <http://www.MedievalNubia.info>;
- 'Photograph/tracing' – this tab will ultimately include photos and/or drawings of particular objects/texts (after obtaining permissions to reproduce them from respective bodies); for the time being the user can find here only references to the best illustrations published so far;
- 'Concordances' – this tab contains a list of simplified references to different publications of a particular text.

Data and description: the database includes 2942 records, which represent all kinds of Christian Nubian written sources, not only those preserving dates. DBMNT was integrated with Trismegistos.org (TM). In the 'Main card' the user will notice the field 'TM' containing a number assigned to the object in the Trismegistos database. Clicking on it will direct the user to a respective record in this important and highly useful collection of metadata of nearly 400,000 ancient and medieval texts. The integration works in both directions, of course, so clicking on the appropriate link in the Trismegistos object card will take the user back to the DBMNT.

Data model: Not available.

Output: Only consultation is allowed.

How to use data: Only consultation is allowed.

Extraction of dataset: From the initial page of the DBMNT and throughout the database, users have the option to either access a specific record directly or explore all records or conduct a search. Choosing the first option leads directly to the text card, while the latter two options present a list of records (either all records or those meeting search criteria). These records include basic information about objects, such as medium type, text type, language, origin, date, contents, and principal bibliographic reference. By clicking the numbered square button on the left-hand side (representing query results, not DBMNT numbers), users can navigate to the object card.

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The database is (almost) fully searchable. In order to conduct a query the user needs to choose a field from a drop-down menu (e.g. 'Provenance'), type in a searched word/phrase (e.g. Faras) and click the 'Apply' button. Additionally, in order to search records that do not contain specific words/phrases in each field, the user needs to tick the 'Not' field (in our example this will result in finding all texts that are not from Faras). The queries can contain multiple (up to ten) conditions, connected with the quantifiers 'and' or 'or'. For example, while searching for all texts from Faras and Qasr Ibrim one must use 'or' ('Provenance' > 'Faras' + 'or' + 'Provenance' > 'Qasr Ibrim'); using 'and' would mean that the search is for texts that are from Faras and Qasr Ibrim at the same time) and while looking for epitaphs from Faras 'and' must be employed ('Provenance' > 'Faras' + 'and' + 'Type of text' > 'epitaph'); using 'or' would result in a list of all epitaphs and all texts from Faras).

Since Nubian medieval texts are predominantly of a religious nature, to select the records of interest, it is sufficient to use the "Type of text" filter in the Search Criteria area. This filter has a drop-down menu that includes various items, many of which refer to religious texts such as apocryphal, biblical, hymns, prayers, and so on. The database gives the possibility to select more one category by using the logical operators.

Card N°23

Project name: Beta masāheft

Institution name: Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities under survey of the Akademie der Wissenschaften in Hamburg.

URL: <https://www.betamasasheft.uni-hamburg.de/>

Description of the project: The project Beta masāheft: Manuscripts of Ethiopia and Eritrea (Schriftkultur des christlichen Äthiopiens: eine multimediale Forschungsumgebung) is a long-term project funded within the framework of the Academies' Programme (coordinated by the Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities) under survey of the Akademie der Wissenschaften in Hamburg. The funding will be provided for 25 years, from 2016–2040. The project is hosted by the Hiob Ludolf Centre for Ethiopian Studies at the University of Hamburg. The project builds upon other initiatives in the study of Ge'ez manuscripts and literature, including the projects Ethio-SPaRe and TraCES, both at the Hiob Ludolf Centre for Ethiopian and Eritrean Studies. The aim of this long-term project is to encode descriptions of manuscripts in existing catalogues, as well as to build critical editions of the text contained, serve images of the manuscripts and especially give the scholars of Eritrean and Ethiopian Studies a research environment where they can contribute data and reuse data with contributions from others in the ways they prefer.

Contacts: aethiopistik@uni-hamburg.de

Abstract of the project: The project aims to achieve a collection of manuscripts, literacy and documentary texts, as well as reference authority files for historical persons and places of Ethiopia and Eritrea. The Beta masāheft research environment is not a box or software providing all the required functionalities but makes use of existing high quality and flexible resources like GitHub (<https://github.com/BetaMasaheft>) and eXist-db as well as well-established standards such as TEI which are openly available, to empower a real and not a virtual research environment, based on digital resources. The database manages data that can benefit any project, with the aim of fostering

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a collaborative culture of exchange. It is hoped that this approach will encourage contributions that positively impact the entire community, promoting shared benefits for all involved. The flexibility and expandability of XML are what allows us to build a research environment as a research environment.

Description of the database: The database is structured on the following schema: eXist-db, a native XML database which allows full data flexibility. This, together with the parallel storage of the data as RDF, makes the data in the project Interoperable. The database supports also several RDF and LOD formats, like DTS (Distributed Texts Services), the Pelagios Gazetteer Interconnection format and Pelagios Annotations. All the project data is maintained in a public GitHub organization with several repositories where anyone can use and contribute to the data. It means data are maintained independently from any application. The only things which should always be shipped with the data are the schema and the guidelines.

Data and description: Data are related to the manuscript tradition and written culture of Ethiopia and Eritrea. The project does not have a data entry form, but participants write XML using the editor of their choice (Oxygen XML Editor or Atom). All the data is managed in GitHub, in an openly accessible organization, <https://github.com/BetaMasaheft>. The application available via <https://betamasasheft.eu> serves this TEI / XML data from an eXist-db instance, which serves alternative formats, which are detailed at <http://betamasasheft.eu/apidoc.html> for all the APIs and <http://betamasasheft.eu/lod.html> for the RDF which is maintained in parallel. The organization of the data in the stored version is functional to its navigation and not meaning-carrying. The .zip file was created by directly compressing the GitHub repositories cloned on a machine. The preferred way of reuse of this data is from its latest version or one of the commits to any branches in the relative repositories in the GitHub organization, and the dump is provided as an additional static version of all the edited data at a given point.

There are seven collections, one for each core entity for the project:

- Manuscripts
- Works
- Narratives
- Institutions
- Places
- Persons
- Authority files

All the files are TEI files and all of them validate to the same Schema and are encoded according to a set of guidelines which are available at

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<https://betamasaheft.eu/Guidelines/>. <https://github.com/BetaMasaheft/guidelines>) detail all the encoding practices of the project with examples

Data model: The project is based on international standards for data and uses open software, following as much as it is possible the FAIR Guiding Principles for both data and software produced. The resources in the project are findable in the FAIR meaning that they all get a unique URI and are described with the rich metadata in TEI, including the URI in all standard formats with which the data is exposed. Data are accessible because it can be retrieved via HTTP, is open and free. Everything is encoded in XML using TEI elements and guidelines. To expose and make accessible the data about images of manuscripts, the project adopted a further standard, IIIF which is a specification for the way in which the information to access images should be presented. Mirador viewer is used to show the information about the images organized in IIIF manifest.

Output: Data are open.

How to use data: Each file contains a specific licence statement with further details if necessary. Where not otherwise stated, the licence is CC-BY-SA 4.0. The web application also provides fully formatted citations of the entries and exportable metadata to facilitate correct citation of individual files within the dataset.

Extraction of dataset: The web application (<https://betamasaheft.eu/>) allow to access the manuscripts, texts, persons, places in several ways. There is the possibility to search art themes present on the works by type of decoration, subject, by person or place referred to in the decoration description.

Card N° 24

Project name: DEChrim (Deconstructing Early Christian Metanarratives) A Platform for the Study of Early Egyptian Christianity

Institution name: MF Vitenskapelig Høyskole, Oslo, Norway.

URL: <https://mf.no/en/node/4339>; <https://4care-skos.mf.no/>

Description of the project: the website is a platform for the centralisation of news and information related to the DEChriM project, where the primary purpose is to host two databases – 4CARE, the 'Fourth Century Archaeological Record of Egypt', and SKOS, the 'South Kharga Oasis Survey'.

Contacts: victor.ghica@mf.no; <https://4care-skos.mf.no/contact/>

Abstract of the project: Thanks to a ERC fund, the project makes available the data contained in two databases respectively related to Egyptian Christianity and to the Kharga Oasis.

DEChriM collaborates with the team of the ERC-funded PATHs ("Tracking Papyrus and Parchment Paths. An Archaeological Atlas of Coptic Literature. Literary Texts in Their Original Context. Production, Copying, Usage, Dissemination and Storage") DARE ("Digital Atlas of the Roman Empire"). And Trismegistos platform, with which most of the 4CARE material is interlinked.

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DEChriM tries to contribute to the emerging world of Linked Open Data for historical resources. With that aim in view, the 4CARE database provides on each of its pages – of both sites and artefacts – downloadable data in machine-readable format (JavaScript Object Notation – JSON).

Description of the database: 4CARE is a repository of all material traces of early Egyptian Christianity dated (or datable) to the fourth century CE. This includes built remnants, i.e., churches and monasteries, as well as movable and immovable artefacts, including textual material, such as papyri, ostraca, and graffiti, as well as non-textual material, comprising ceramic, textiles, jewelry etc. The database is formatted as a GIS database, meaning these material traces are associated with their geographic location. As the product of ongoing work of the members of DEChriM, 4CARE will thus continue to be updated throughout the course of the remaining three years of the project. SKOS, a project of the Institut français d'archéologie orientale (IFAO) is also a GIS database, comprising the results of the largest scale archaeological survey ever conducted in Egypt, covering an area of c. 5500km². Unlike 4CARE, SKOS is not exclusively related to fourth century Christianity, nor exclusively to Christianity. Instead, it spans the entirety of human history in the southern area of the Kharga Oasis. Despite the time, effort and dedication required to complete such a survey, the results were never published due to the untimely death of Michel Wuttman, the director and driving force behind the project. After being somewhat forgotten, interest was reignited through DEChriM, which was able to provide a platform and financing for the finalisation of the project, which, in addition to the database, will include two printed volumes.

Data and description: 4Care database includes 80 sites and 1743 artifacts. The material selected for inclusion can be divided into two large groups: textual and non-textual objects. All the sites included in the database (called Places) are described on a specific page, which contains several descriptors:

- o toponyms in several languages, both ancient and modern;
- o an internal numeric identifier (DEChriM ID);
- o external numeric identifiers from other relevant gazetteers (Trismegistos, Pleiades, PATHs Atlas);
- o an ancient name considered as standard (in Greek or Coptic);
- o geographical coordinates (expressed in decimal degrees);
- o the dates of the occupation (expressed in termini, which are either absolute, when available, or relative);
- o the type of settlement (...);
- o the criteria considered in the dating of the occupation of the site;
- o a description providing an overview of the main areas and monuments of the site;
- o a very brief summary of the archaeological research carried out on the site;
- o a bibliography, which, although not exhaustive, tends to cover the most relevant studies.

Each archaeological site is accompanied also by external links to websites that refer to it. The internal links connect a site with the archaeological material associated with it that is included in the database. The section Json data provides elements of selected machine readable information. A selection of maps and photos accompany each site. Finally, the section 3D models includes photogrammetric models and 3D reconstructions of areas of sites or of specific monuments. These can be visualised in a Sketchfab window in three different resolutions.

Christian artefacts dated to the fourth century found in Egypt, regardless of the location of their production. The former category (Class: Textual) contains three sorts of texts (Text content): Literary; Subliterary; Documentary. The latter category comprises a variety of object types. All objects are further defined by Material type, while textual artefacts are also characterised by, for papyrological texts, the Writing medium involved: Codex; Sheet/roll; Label; Ostrakon; Tablet; and, for epigraphical

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texts, the Writing technique: Dipinto; Graffito; Inscription. Finally, the Language is indicated for textual artefacts.

SKOS includes a total of 290 registered sites, of which 266 are located in the southern part of Kharga, previously mainly known by few sites such as Dush or Shams el-Din. To these 290 archaeological sites are associated 3164 sub-sites (Sous-sites).

Data model: The database uses external link to Trismegistos, Pleaides, Papyri.info e PAThs, BnF Gallica

Output: the search produces a webpage with information and the possibility to download the json format. It is possible to access, by external links, to other platforms.

How to use data: the information is made accessible online.

Extraction of dataset: In 4care database it is possible use the functions of search or advances search. A drop-down menu allows to search in base of ID ancient or modern place name, date, description and archaeological research. SKOS allows a simple search by using a keyword for ancient or modern name or typology. In order to select religious texts, it is possible to use the filters. In the Advanced Search area, the filter Class has a drop-down menu where one can select liturgical objects and textual documents. The filter Selection Criteria includes more than one categories related to religious like Liturgical, Biblical, Hagiographic and so on.

Card N°25

Project name: BerlPap (The Berlin Papyrus Database)

Institution name: Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis der griechischen Papyrusurkunden Ägyptens (HGV) with the additional project "Übersetzung Berliner Griechische Urkunden (BGU) I-IV"; Papyrus-Portal; Leuven Database of Ancient Books (LDAB); Trismegistos; Papyri.info; Aristarchus, Scholia Minora; New Testament Virtual Manuscript Room.

URL: <https://berlpap.smb.museum/?lang=en>

Description of the project: The Berlin Papyrus Database is a project sponsored by the German Research Foundation (DFG) for the inventory and digitization of Greek and Latin texts of the Berlin Papyrus Collection. In 2023, the Coptic literary texts were added, which were processed by the Coptic Manuscripts Unit of the Academy Project Union Catalogue of Oriental Manuscripts.

Contacts: berlpap@smb.spk-berlin.de

Abstract of the project: The Berlin Collection is significant not only for its substantial number of papyri, some of which are highly relevant, but also for its possession of important archives. These collections of documentary and literary texts, gathered since antiquity, provide insight into various aspects of Greco-Roman Egyptian culture, including everyday life, economy, law, and administration. Some archives, like that of the Apion family, offer the opportunity to trace family histories over generations. Many Berlin texts are linked to ostraca and papyri from other collections due to shared excavation sites and antiquity dealers splitting up papyrus lots. Consequently, archives and dossiers are scattered across various collections worldwide. The Berlin Papyrus Collection encompasses texts

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from numerous archives, including the Abinnaeus archive, the royal bank of Thebes archive, the Milon praktor archive, the Taurinos archive, and the administrative archive of Theadelphia.

Description of the database: BerlPap offers all classicists and those interested in antiquity direct access to thousands of texts from Egypt in the Greco-Roman period (4th cent. BCE – 7th cent. AD). These collections of documentary and/or literary texts have been gathered already in antiquity and enable to investigate different aspects of culture, everyday life, economy, law and the administration of Greco-Roman Egypt not only by means of single texts, but also through the context of several papyri.

Data and description: All originals are scanned in high resolution on an overhead scanner. All data about content, dating, provenience, and acquisition are added.

Data model: There exists external links to other websites that show the same resource such as Trismegistos, Papyri.info, LDAB.

Output: By means of linking metadata and pictures to other databases and the homepages of partners transcriptions and even translations become available for users.

How to use data: The featured images are available for all those interested in their study. However, the images from this website are not to be published directly. Images ready for publication will be provided, if requested with sufficient notice.

Extraction of dataset: The webpage has search functions to explore the data. It is possible to insert a keyword or indicate inventory number, date, provenance, material, language, acquisition, genre. In the latter case, a drop-down menu allows to select the type of text like Christian texts.

Card N°26

Project name: Brooklyn Museum Open Collections

Institution name: Brooklyn Museum

URL: <https://www.brooklynmuseum.org/opencollection/collections/5>

Description of the project: The website offers the possibility to visualize the following online collections of the Brooklyn Museum: American Art; Arts of Africa; Arts of the Americas; Arts of the Islamic World; Arts of the Pacific Islands; Arts of Asia; Contemporary Art; Decorative Arts and Design; Egyptian, Classical, Ancient Near Eastern Art; Elizabeth A. Sackler Center for Feminist Art; European Art; Libraries and Archives; Photography

Contacts: information@brooklynmuseum.org or 718.638.5000.

Description of the database: The Brooklyn Museum uses the Brooklyn Museum Collection API that is a set of services that one can use to display Brooklyn Museum collection images and data in own applications (<https://www.brooklynmuseum.org/opencollection/api/>). It consists of a RESTful api, set of methods that returns structured data (JSON) and links to images from the collections.

To perform an action using the API, you need to issue an HTTP request to this base URL: <https://www.brooklynmuseum.org/api/v2>. To access an API key is also required.

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Data and description: 8653 records are included in the database. Each record is described with different metadata: dates, medium, dynasty, period, dimensions, collections, accession number, credit line, provenance, catalogue description, museum location, caption, image, rights statement.

Data model: Not available.

Output: It is possible to download the images in jpg format.

How to use data: Creative Commons-BY.

Extraction of dataset: it is possible to use the keyword search or advanced search. The search functions do not include a typology of objects that allow to filter data of the selected collection.

Card N°27

Project name: British Museum Collection

Institution name: The British Museum

URL: <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection>

Description of the institution: The British Museum is one of the largest museums that is dedicated to human history and culture. Currently a work in progress, the British Museum database is “an inventory of the Museum’s collection and aims to record what is known about it”. To date, the database contains more than 2.1 million records with new records, updates and images added every week.

Contacts: collectiondatabase@britishmuseum.org

Abstract of the project: Collection online allows access to almost four and a half million objects in more than two million records. High-definition images can be enlarged and examined in detail.

Description of the database: The database is based on the British Museum's collection management tool, where they record what they know about the collection. It was created for the Museum to store information for its own use, and is therefore full of specialised terms, abbreviations and shorthand.

In some cases, catalogue entries and descriptions from more than 250 years of the Museum's history are included as part of a record. This can include terms that the Museum would no longer choose to use. We aim to ensure that all language used is clearly presented in its historical context.

The database used is Merlin.

Data and description: Each record is described indicating the object's descriptive fields; identification numbers; bibliography; the presence of inscriptions or marks; geographical provenance; production and antiquity; acquisition provenance; associations in terms of people, places, events, and titles; location, exhibition and loans; conservation and administrative data.

Data model: The data has also been organised using the CIDOC-CRM. Resources are provided with a URI. The system uses the British Museum Thesauri (<https://terminology.collectionstrust.org.uk/British-Museum-objects/>)

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Output: one can select 'Download results', in a search containing up to 10,000 records, to download a spreadsheet of those records.

How to use data: Data are Open, for non-commercial and educational, academic, scholarly, or motivated by private interest only. Users are required to attach copyright notices to the materials marking them "© Trustees of the British Museum" unless otherwise indicated on their website.

Extraction of dataset: The dataset is available through the Museum's web. It is possible to use the search box. After running a search, one ends up with a set of results that can be filtered to narrow down and find what one is looking for. In order to select the religious texts of the Nile Valley, one can type "text" in the search box, then filter the results according to culture/period/dynasty and the subject like religious/belief.

Card N°28

Project name: The Musawwarat Graffiti Archive

Institution name: Max-Planck-Institute for the History of Science and Humboldt-Universität.

URL: https://musawwaratgraffiti.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/graffitidb/using_database

Description of the project: The Musawwarat Graffiti Archive, via its 'Graffiti in Place Database', provides access to a large part of the research database of the Musawwarat Graffiti Project. The graffiti were engraved on the walls of the complex at Musawwarat es Sufra, in Sudan. The website gives many information about the project and data and the procedures used to archive data.

Contacts: Not available.

Abstract of the project: The Archive is dedicated to the digital preservation, publication and promotion of African cultural heritage. Traces of the movement and transformation of ideas and knowledge within the ancient world are manifest in the thousands of graffiti that were incised over more than 2000 years into the walls of the so-called Great Enclosure, a unique, labyrinthine building complex forming the centre of the site. This multi-layered archive of images, inscriptions and markings reflects various aspects of the ever changing life-worlds of the people of the past. It also forms a treasure trove for present seekers of knowledge, be they researchers or members of the interested global public.

Description of database: Different tools were brought together to create a dynamic environment to present research data in the process from 'raw data' to an online 'publication':

- 1) A database for entering systematic graffiti-focussed information. Information is entered in a custom FileMaker database. The database holds information about all photos, blocks, walls, and graffiti and their relations. All data from the FileMaker database is exported into a PostgreSQL database for the web display.
- 2) A web presentation environment for informational texts and images as well as search and 'browse' access to the database and all photos. The web frontend runs on the Open Source ZOPE application server.

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3) The web environment also allows the creation of hot-spots on images as an additional way of visually navigating the site by clicking through from ground plans to images on the single block level, enhanced with information from the database.

4) All photos are presented using an image viewer allowing the user to zoom in and inspect images at the highest resolution even on low-bandwidth connections.

Data and description: Database entries describe nearly 4000 graffiti entities on the 1599 sandstone blocks of Temple 300. The archive contains more than 2,500 photographs as well as 900 drawings of the temple and its graffiti. Not all graffiti entities have been fully described and annotated, and some may need to be re-assigned to a different date or motif category as research progresses. Image files as well as related descriptive data are the prime data types. However, according to the webpage indications, the Archive is planned to also present additional data types in the future, such as 3D-models and RTI-files. All image files are stored on a central file server at the MPIWG and presented via the Open Source Digilib image server. The image viewer allows the user to zoom in and view images at high resolution, and to annotate and reference images for online publication.

Data model: Terms and categories for date and motif have been defined to describe and search the resources.

Output: Images can be downloaded.

How to use data: Text and photos (this excludes photos taken by Pawel Wolf and photos depicting people) appearing on this website are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 License (CC BY-SA 4.0).

Extraction of the dataset: The access to the 'Graffiti in Place Database' is provided through two different entry points: the 'explore' and the 'browse' functions. The interactive 'explore' section presents the graffiti in their exact spatial context by letting the visitor select an area of interest on an overview map of the Great Enclosure and then click on individual walls and through to the block level. The search function allows to search resources according to 'location', 'date/period' or 'motif' criteria. The 'location' function provides graffiti search results at the complex, wall, or block levels, allowing the user to refine search results via drop-down menus. 'Date/period' searches bring up those graffiti for which an approximate date has been entered into the database. The 'motif' search function enables the user to search for specific graffiti motif categories, motif types and motifs as they are defined in the motif thesaurus that was developed for the description of the Musawwarat graffiti. Searches can be refined via drop-down menus.

Card N°29

Project name: Die Aegyptiaca der Universität Göttingen im Sammlungsportal

Institution name: University of Göttingen

URL: https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/sammlung/slg_1050/

Description of the project: The Aegyptiaca of the University of Göttingen, are distributed in different collections. Mummies, parts of mummies and grave equipment are kept in the Archaeological Collections, the Anthropological Collection and in the Collection of the Center Anatomy. By contrast,

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most of the objects in the Department of Egyptology and Coptology today are permanent loans from the Ethnological Collection and still bear corresponding inventory numbers.

Contacts: aegypten@uni-goettingen.de; www.aegyptologie.uni-goettingen.de; Seminar für Ägyptologie und Koptologie, Kulturwissenschaftliches Zentrum, Prof. Dr. Heike Behlmer, Heinrich-Düker-Weg 14, 37073 Göttingen, Tel.: 0551 39-24561.

Abstract of the project: The project consists of a website of the collection of Aegyptiaca of the University of Göttingen. As part of the internship program "Wissensthing online" 2017, high-resolution photographs of all objects with inventory numbers were created. The cataloguing data of the pieces included in the 2005 catalogue were transferred to the Göttingen collection database, and records for other objects were created.

Data and description: The website presents 66 records. Each one is described in a specific webpage where there is the main information about the object such as title, inventory number, location, taxonomy and keywords, description, dimension, material, technique, production and links to other webpages.

Data model: The model is based on LIDO, Iconclass (it appears in the filters), the DNB Katalog der Deutschen National Bibliothek as controlled vocabulary, GVK(Gemeinsamer Verbundkatalog: the cataloguing database of the Common Library Network and the Library Network Southwest Germany) for the bibliography, Geonames, link to Wikipedia to describe the themes; IIF for the images (For instance: https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/objekt/record_kuniweb_926813/1/-/)

How to use data: CC-BY-SA 4.0

Extraction of dataset: In the search box, you can enter a keyword to specify your search.

Card N°30

Project name: The Monumental Inscriptions of Historic Cairo

URL: <https://islamicinscriptions.cultnat.org/default>

Description of the project: According to the information on the website, the initial aim of this project was to photograph, transcribe and translate the unpublished inscriptions in pre-1800 monuments in Cairo. In addition it was hoped to record those inscriptions, published or not, most in danger of disappearing because of their fragile state of conservation.

Contacts: there is a form for contacts, <https://islamicinscriptions.cultnat.org/ContactUs>

Description of database: The dataset is organized in inscriptions, monuments and references. Each field include metadata for describing the text, the object and references. Inscription heading, include the text in English and Arabic (which can be printed separately). It also has thumbnails of photographs which can be clicked on for enlargements, and for printing. The Monument heading give details of the monument in which the inscription is located and has thumbnails of drawings showing the location of the inscription on the monument. The drawings can be clicked on for enlargements, and for printing. The References heading shows bibliographic references to previous publications. No metadata standards have been used.

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Data and description: Not available.

Data model: Not available.

Output: text, jpg and pdf files.

How to use data: it is possible to read information, print or save as pdf the text and copy, print or save as jpg the image.

Extraction of the dataset: the user may search by the fields in Inscriptions or Monuments on the initial screen, but not both at the same time. Several fields are common to both, namely Patron and Hijri and Common Era date ranges. In Inscription, it is possible to search by the number of inscription, text in English or Arabic, by style, material and type that have different drop down lists. The list of the field Type includes the topic "religious" but also some other topics that can be considered collaterals, such as "religious poetry", "Quranic", "Psalm", "Blessing". The search brings up a number of results which can be sorted by Inscription or Monument.

Clicking on an Inscription Number in a search result brings you to a page with detailed information with three headings: Inscription, Monument and References

Card N°31

Project name: Princeton University Art Museum Collections

Institution name: Princeton University

URL: <https://artmuseum.princeton.edu/search/collections>

Description of the institution: With a collecting history that extends back to the 1750s, the Museum is one of the few university art museums of truly universal scope. Its collections, which number more than 112,000 works in all media, range from ancient to contemporary and span the globe.

Contacts: cathryng@princeton.edu (for Online collections feedback)

Abstract of the project: In 2017 the Princeton University Art Museum launched an Application Programming Interface (API) with the goal of making the Museum's collections of more than 112,000 works of art readily available for students, instructors, curators, and developers around the world.

Description of database: For each work that enters the collections, the Museum records a set of information documenting core characteristics, such as the artist who created the work and the date when it was created; physical characteristics such as its size and medium; and narrative summaries of any analysis of the work that has been carried out by Museum curators or other scholars. For the majority of works, this text-based data is accompanied by digital images produced by the Museum that provide a visual representation of the work. The API aggregates these resources and makes them available for developers to integrate into their own applications, opening up a broad range of possibilities for engagement with the collections. This system is an important tool for students, who have developed remarkable projects with widely different applications. <https://github.com/Princeton-University-Art-Museum/puam-api-docs/blob/master/README.md>

Data and description: Each record includes a brief description which want to present the object like title, period, culture, and material. This brief description can be copied as text. Then there is a section

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called Information with the main metadata: title, object number, medium, dates, dimension, credit line, culture, period, inscriptions, type, provenance, subjects, bibliographic entries.

Data model: Not available.

Output: Images and text-based data.

How to use data: The images on the site are of various types and copyrights attached. Images that are on the public domain can be downloaded “for personal and educational use” but no alteration is allowed. Thumbnails of images are displayed under fair use as defined in the United States copyright laws. Any use of other copyrighted materials requires the permission of the copyright holders, Visual Artists and Galleries Association Inc, (VAGA) or Art Resource. Attribution is required. The images can be cited by including the author and source of the images as they would material from any printed work, with the URL, “artmuseum.princeton.edu.”.

Extraction of dataset: The dataset is available through the Museum’s webpage. Using the search box and typing “religious text” the system provides a list of results which include all records preserved in the museums that have as Subject “religious text”. Then it is possible filter them according to the culture such as Egyptian (ancient) or Islamic. However, looking at the whole Egyptian collection, not all results are provided in this type of search. It depends on how the texts are described.

Card N°32

Project name: The Walters Art Museum Online Collection

Institution name: The Walters Art Museum

URL: <https://art.thewalters.org/browse/category/>; <https://www.thedigitalwalters.org/>

Description of the institution: The Walters Art Museum’s collection spans more than seven millennia, from 5,000 BCE to the 21st century, and encompasses 36,000 objects. This extraordinary collection is rich in works that represent the height of human creativity and artistry, ranging from mummies to arms and armor, from old master paintings to Art Nouveau jewelry around the globe and across ages.

Contacts: digitalresources@thewalters.org.

Abstract of the project: The Walters Art Museum houses an extraordinary collection of some 850 illuminated manuscripts from diverse cultures around the world. Full digital surrogates of many of these manuscripts are available on this website accessible through <https://www.thedigitalwalters.org/>.

Description of database: Not available.

Data and description: Nearly all of the Walters’ collection of 128 Islamic codices and 60 loose leaves are available on the Digital Walters. All of them are accompanied by detailed manuscript description information in machine-readable TEI format. Because of their fragile condition or their inordinately large or small sizes, however, a few of our Islamic manuscripts could not be imaged as part of the Islamic Digital Resource project. The Walters is now digitizing its English, Dutch, German, Armenian, Byzantine and Ethiopian manuscripts for the Parchment to Pixel project. As with the Islamic

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manuscripts, conservation and size considerations may prohibit the digitization of some of these manuscripts.

Manuscript images and descriptions appear on this site as they are completed. Images are added frequently, as the digitization takes place. TEI manuscript descriptions also appear as they become available, but this may be as long as two years after the images are added, as their delivery depends on the completing to the cataloging and an editorial review process.

Data model: Two types of descriptive metadata are provided for manuscripts and manuscript images: Dublin Core for basic metadata and TEI P5 manuscript descriptions for cataloging information.

Basic metadata is provided for manuscripts and individual archival TIFF images using Dublin Core Metadata Initiative elements. This basic metadata is presented on the manuscript's HTML page and is also stored in the ImageDescription tag of the TIFF header of each individual archival image. The following elements are used.

- Identifier: the shelf mark for manuscripts (e.g., W.582), and the image serial number for images (e.g., W582_000001)
- Creator: always the Walters Art Museum
- Contributor: one entry for each project participant responsible for the creation of the manuscript's data set
- Date: the date of web page or image creation
- Title: the title of the manuscript (e.g., "Walters Ms. W.579, Prayer")
- Description: a description of the manuscript or image
- Source: source of the object used to create the image or image collection
- Type: Image for individual images; Collection for all images of a manuscript
- Format: image/tiff for images, text/html for a manuscript web page
- Subject: keywords describing the manuscript or imaged folio
- Rights: license and usage terms

Manuscript cataloging incorporates not only the identification of the author, title of works, date of origin and provenance of the manuscripts, but also detailed descriptions intended to aid the palaeographer, codicologist, art historian, historian, and philologist. A description of the manuscript cataloging, with technical and non-technical detail, is given in the document ManuscriptDescription.html.

Output: images in jpg and tiff, pdf.

How to use data: Images in the museum's online collection are made available under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. Copyright is waived and the museum "allow for unrestricted use of digital images and metadata by any person, for any purpose ". Proper citation and giving credit to "The Walters Art Museum" is required when using images.

About the Walters manuscript images and descriptions, they are licensed for use under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported License and the GNU Free Documentation License.

Extraction of dataset: Through their online collections, users can search or browse images in several ways, which include category, date, creator, medium and tags. Users can also login using their Facebook account to create their own online collections.

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Project name: The Israel Museum Collection

Institution name: The Israel Museum, Jerusalem

URL: <https://museum.imj.org.il/Imagine/collections/index.asp#ImaginativeAccess>

Description of the institution: Founded in 1965, the Israel Museum is “the largest cultural institution in the State of Israel “. The museum houses encyclopaedic collections, ranging from pre-history to the present day in archaeology, fine arts and Jewish art.

Contacts: info@imj.org.il

Abstract of the project: The digital image database of the Museum, IMAGINE, allows users to search and browse the collections by exhibitions, collections or departments.

Description of the database: Not available.

Data and description: Records are described with a text.

Data model: No metadata and no vocabularies are available.

Output: Pdf file with the image and information about the object.

How to use data: text and photos copyright © The Israel Museum, Jerusalem, 1995 – 2024.

Extraction of dataset: The search function allows users to locate existing resources using the basic search or search the collection by artist name. It is possible to select the collection, the department or exhibition.

Card N°34

Project name: Art Institute of Chicago Collections

Institution name: Art Institute of Chicago

URL: <https://www.artic.edu/collection>

Description of the institution: The Art Institute of Chicago was founded as both a museum and school for fine arts around 1879. Today, it houses more than 300,000 works of art in their permanent collections, ranging from Chinese bronzes to contemporary design and from textiles to installation art.

Contacts: collections@artic.edu

Abstract of the project: the Art Institute of Chicago provides access to all of public data through a single, unified API. This API is powered by a data hub, a system built to collect public information from a number of different internal systems. In the API, one can find data about collections, digital publications, in-gallery interactives, mobile apps, shop products, events, and more. For a number of reasons, users might want to have a copy of our entire dataset to work with locally, instead of querying the API. In order to obtain this dataset, it has been provided a full data dump of the API here, via the repository of GitHub (<https://github.com/art-institute-of-chicago/api-data/blob/master/README.md>)

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Description of the database: Not available.

Data and description: The digital collection contains more than 80,000 images, which can be searched or browsed by categories. The website also allows to sign up for an account and make an own art collection by selecting artworks and adding notes about them. It is possible to save the “collections” to revisit in the future or share them with your friends

Data model: Not available.

Output: Data can be consulted from the site.

How to use data: Under Fair Use, users can use the site content for limited non-commercial, educational, and personal use only. All copyright and other proprietary notices contained on the images are to be retained. Citation is required by including the author, source of the materials and other descriptive information.

Extraction of dataset: the user can access public domain images using the advanced search filters on the Collection page. Among the many filters is a checkbox to limit your search results to only public domain artworks. The user can use this checkbox to view all public domain artworks, refine existing keyword searches, or combine it with other filters such as artist, date, and medium. By selecting the filter Artists there is the possibility to choose Ancient Egyptian that include 1048 items. The list of results can be further filtered applying the filter Subjects. In this case there is not the definition “religious” or “religious text” but subjects like Gods (deities) or Hieroglyphs. Otherwise, there exists the subject Religion or religious but selecting it, it is impossible to visualize records from the Ancient Egypt.

Card N°35

Project name: LACMA Collections

Institution name: Los Angeles County Museum of Art

URL: <https://collections.lacma.org/>

Description of the project: LACMA is the largest art museum in the western United States, with a collection of nearly 152,000 objects across different media, region and periods such as Egyptian, Greek, Roman and Etruscan art, Asian art, American and Latin American art, decorative arts and design, photography, and modern and contemporary art. Committed to showcasing a multitude of art histories, LACMA exhibits and interprets works of art from new and unexpected points of view that are informed by the region’s rich cultural heritage and diverse population.

Contacts: library@lacma.org

Abstract of the project: The Balch Art Research Library is the repository of LACMA's institutional archive of records related to the museum's past exhibitions and administrative history. The library includes:

- General Collection—exhibition catalogs, catalogues raisonnés, auction catalogs, periodicals, art reference books, artist files

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- Special Collections—artists' books and special-format ephemera, rare publications and fine editions, portfolios, exhibition posters
- Online resources— growing collection of e-books, digitized materials, and subscription databases (accessible on-site)

As archival collections are processed, finding aids describing the nature and contents of each collection are posted to the Online Archive of California, a database of archival collections from all over the state of California.

Description of the database: Not available.

Data and description: The digital collections provide access to more than 53,000 images of artworks with more than 20,000 that LACMA believes to be in the public domain.

Data model: Not available.

Output: jpg, tiff

How to use data: Images contained on the LACMA site are either (1) images of works that LACMA believes are in the public domain ("Public Domain High Resolution Image Available"), or (2) protected by copyright ("Protected Content"). Images on public domain can be used without restrictions, while protected content can only be used for "non-commercial personal use". Citation is required for both types of content and should include the URL www.lacma.org and any proprietary notices accompanying the image.

Extraction of dataset: Users can search and filter the results by artist, classification, curatorial area, periods and location. In order to extract resources that are compliant with WP10 research, it's necessary to select the "Curatorial Area" filter and indicate "Egyptian art." The system then provides a list of 1506 results. The "Classification" filter may assist in identifying specific texts such as tablets, but it's important to note that many inscriptions appear in other categories as well.

Card N°36

Project name: University Cambridge Digital Library

Institution name: University of Cambridge

URL: <https://cudl.lib.cam.ac.uk/collections/ethiopianmanuscripts/1>

Description of the project: The Cambridge Digital Library is a project operated by the Cambridge University Library designed to make items from the unique and distinctive collections of Cambridge University Library available online.

Contacts: dl-feedback@lib.cam.ac.uk

Description of the database: The eXtensible Text Framework (XTF) and Goobi for digitising and indexing the data.

Data and description: Data consists of image and metadata xml. Records are provided by URI. The webpage of the record includes images (in the case of a manuscripts, it includes the image of all pages), description of the object, contents, thumbnails, transcription, translation and metadata.

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Data model: Data are primarily in METS, MODS and TEI formats.

Output: image, xml.

How to use data: CC BY-NC 3.0

Extraction of dataset: Users can use the search function and filter the results.

Card N°37

Project name: The Metropolitan Museum of Art collection

Institution name: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York

URL: <https://www.metmuseum.org>

Description of the institution: The Metropolitan Museum of Art creates, organizes, and disseminates a broad range of digital images and data that document the rich history of the Museum, its collection, exhibitions, events, people, and activities.

Contacts: openaccess@metmuseum.org.

Abstract of the project: The Metropolitan Museum of Art provides www.metmuseum.org and its subdomains (including websites accessed through mobile devices as well as downloadable mobile applications) and application program interfaces ("APIs") (collectively, the "Websites") in support of the Museum's mission to collect, preserve, study, exhibit, and encourage appreciation for and advance knowledge of works of art.

Description of the database: The Metropolitan Museum of Art provides select datasets of information on more than 470,000 artworks in its Collection for unrestricted commercial and non-commercial use.

Data and description: data are provided with URI. On the web page of a record, there is a description of it, and some metadata which give general information, provenance, exhibition history and references.

Data model: metadata standards (variable1): Nomisma, CRMdig.
<https://github.com/nomisma/data/blob/master/id/metmuseum.rdf>

Output: The datasets are available in CSV format, encoded in UTF-8. While UTF-8 is the standard for multilingual character encodings. <https://github.com/metmuseum/openaccess>. It is possible to download images by the webpage.

How to use data: Images of artworks in the Museum's collection fall into two categories:

1. images of works the Museum believes to be in the public domain, or those to which the Museum waives any copyright it might have
2. images of works the Museum knows to be under copyright or other restrictions

The database makes available data from the entire online collection—both works it believes to be in the public domain and those under copyright or other restrictions—including basic information such as title, artist, date, medium, and dimensions.

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Extraction of dataset: Users can employ the search function and apply filters to refine their results. When applying the keywords "religious texts," the system generates a list of results from different collections. However, it's worth noting that not all data are included; for example, the entire Ethiopian collection is excluded from the list.

Card N°38

Project name: National Museum of Antiquities Collection

Institution name: National Museum of Antiquities, Leiden, The Netherlands

URL: <https://www.rmo.nl/en/collection/search-collection/>

Description of the institution: The Dutch National Museum of Antiquities of Leiden (Rijksmuseum van Oudheden) is the national centre of archaeology where the audience can appreciate the cultures of ancient Egypt, the Near East, the classical world and the early Netherlands. The Dutch National Museum of Antiquities has some 180,000 objects in its collection, divided into four areas:

1. Egypt and Nubia
2. Classical Antiquity (Greeks, Romans, and Etruscans)
3. The Ancient Near East
4. The Netherlands (prehistory, the Roman period, and the Middle Ages)

Contacts: <https://www.rmo.nl/en/organisation/contact/>

Abstract of the project: The website presents the museum collections and exhibitions in an interactive way by means of timelines, Google Maps, Zoomify galleries and audiotours. Now, these elements are available in the Dutch version only (https://www.museumsandtheweb.com/nominee/rijksmuseum_van_oudheden_dutch_national_museum_antiq)

Description of the database: not available.

Data and description: the database of the Dutch National Museum of Antiquities, Leiden, counts more than 140,000 objects. The records are provided with URI and are described on a web page where it is indicated the title, keywords, main information about the object, and the literature. Even if the site is available in 10 languages, the database is only available in Dutch. Thus, one needs to search using Dutch keywords.

Data model: not available

Output: on the web site it is possible to download the jpg image, but metadata is not available for download.

How to use data: Collection data and images from the National Museum of Antiquities are freely available for re-use by developers under a Creative Commons license. Object descriptions (metadata) and images (content) are made available under a CCo licence.

Extraction of dataset: the webpage of the museum has search functions to explore the data. It is possible to insert a keyword or indicate the accession number of the object, the object name, material, period, findspot, or the departments. Applying the general terms "Religieuze tekst" and

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selecting the department Egypt and Nubia, only two records have been found. While using only “tekst” and the same department, it provides 848 records.

Card N°39

Project name: The Arabic Papyrology Database

Institution name: Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich, Institute of Near and Middle Eastern Studies with generous support of the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, New York; University of Zurich, Institute of Asian and Oriental Studies with generous support of the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, New York and Faculty of Arts, University of Zurich.

URL: <https://www.apd.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/apd/project.jsp>

Description of the project: The Arabic Papyrology Database (APD) gives the access to editions of and research on pre-modern Arabic documents written on papyrus, parchment, paper, etc., an often untapped treasure for almost every aspect of the Islamic World from the 7th up to the 16th century CE.

Contacts: andreas.kaplony@lmu.de

Abstract of the project: The Arabic Papyrology Database is the first digital compilation of Arabic documents on papyrus, parchment, paper, etc. It is a non-commercial project run under the patronage of the International Society for Arabic Papyrology (ISAP) and a partner of the Trismegistos metadata project of Greek, Demotic, Coptic, Arabic, etc. documents. Access is free via the Internet. The Arabic Papyrology Database is continuously enlarged. There is webpage with the guidelines for preparing texts and implement them in the database: https://www.naher-osten.uni-muenchen.de/forschung/papyrologie/apd_guidelines/index.html

Description of the database: not available

Data and description: The Arabic Papyrology Database comprises a total of 13382 documents. Through DOCUMENTS tab, you will be able to search all 13382 documents by their metadata as for instance their edition name, inventory number, kind, material, place and date of origin. Through TEXT, you might search the Arabic full text of 4383 documents by the spelling of words and word combinations as on the document, by their transliteration, lemma (lexicon entry), root and stem; non-standard forms have not been standardized but will be found by their standard forms. LEXICON gives you direct access to all lemmata and roots. In TYPES, 6900 documents have been attributed to 460 formal document types and you will be able to search documents by their phrases and layout elements; we fully marked up the layout on 460 documents, and text structure on 1469 documents. PALEO is a visual tool to compare scripts while sitting in front of the originals: you might search 1002 documents by their script angles. BIBLIO gives you access to all 3304 monographs, collective volumes and papers we know about including all their reviews.

Data model: Not available. The system uses Trismegistos to link the place names.

Output: The user can search documents and read the text.

How to use data: Free access.

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Extraction of dataset: The user can use the search functions typing keywords or/and use the drop-down menu. The search functions are present for each tab Document, Text, Lexicon, Types, Paleo, Biblio. In the tab Document it is possible to search for Kind of document. The classification does not include religious texts, but users can select categories such as prayers, pilgrimage certificates, and amulets.

Card N°40

Project name: Trismegistos

Institution name: Trismegistos' information is based upon a variety of partner projects and institutions, to date more than 150 in number (January 2024).

URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/index.php>; <https://www.trismegistos.org/about.php>

Description of the project: Trismegistos (TM) is a metadata platform for the study of texts from the Ancient World, coordinated and maintained by the KU Leuven research group of Ancient History. It aims to surmount barriers of language and discipline in the study of texts from the ancient world, particularly late period Egypt and the Nile valley (roughly BC 800 - 800 AD). Firstly, it functions as an aggregator of metadata for which it also links to other projects. Secondly, it aims to provide stable identifiers for all types of information about the Ancient World, e.g. texts, places and people. With its unique id numbers and stable URI's, Trismegistos sets standards for and bridges the gap between different digital representations of Ancient World texts. This strategy enables TM to offer all its metadata as linked open data and attract other projects to connect with TM. Trismegistos as a metadata database focus on providing information about texts, not the transliterated text itself

Contacts: mark.depauw@kuleuven.be

Abstract of the project: Trismegistos has a variety of partner projects and institutions. Most partners have their own website to link out. Some partners provide updates of their information on a regular, usually yearly basis; most just send their new records to unambiguously identify them through the unique TM-identification number, e.g. TM 4523.

Description of the database: Several aspects of the Texts database have been elaborated during successive projects (see History) and have become separate databases linked with the core Trismegistos Texts database.

1. The Collections database, built on the Leuven Homepage of Papyrus Collections, is a set of currently 4288 modern institutional and private collections of texts and their 2882815 inventory numbers (Last access: 05/04/024). It is searchable both separately and in the Texts database.
2. The Archives database, built on the Leuven Homepage of Papyrus Archives, is a set of currently 628 collections of texts in antiquity, mainly in Egypt, and the 22060 texts that are part of these archives. (Last access: 05/04/024). It is searchable separately, leading to the texts themselves.
3. The People database, building on the Prosopographia Ptolemaica, is a complex set of prosopographical and onomastic databases. It currently contains 552919 attestations of personal names of non-royal individuals living in Egypt between BC 800 and AD 800, including all languages and scripts and written on any surface. (Last access: 05/04/024).

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4. The Places database, expanding the geographic database of the Fayum project, is a set of currently 62214 places in Egypt and increasingly also outside (in view of the expansion of TM to the ancient world in general). It contains the currently 261199 attestations of toponyms in texts from Egypt (BC 800 – AD 800) but is also linked to the provenance field in Trismegistos Texts. (Last access: 05/04/024).

5. Finally, because abbreviations are often different in the various disciplines, a Bibliography has been established to address many of the short references used in Trismegistos. Conversely, its purpose is also to facilitate searching for all texts within a specific publication. Its coverage is patchy except for the publications dealing with Demotic and Abnormal Hieratic, where the Demotistische Literaturübersicht provides a much higher standard of bibliographic information.

Trismegistos: database structure

Legend Trismegistos website:

<div style="background-color: #c00000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">TEXTS</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of all texts with a unique Trismegistos number (TM ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #c00000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">TM ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/text/TM ID</div>	<div style="background-color: #008000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">PEOPLE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of names of people with a unique Trismegistos Name number (NAM ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #008000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">NAM ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/name/NAM ID</div>
<div style="background-color: #c00000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">COLLECTIONS</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of museums and private collections with a unique Trismegistos Collections number (COLL ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #c00000; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">COLL ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/collection/COLL ID</div>	<div style="background-color: #000080; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">PLACES</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of places with a unique Trismegistos Geo number (GEO ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #000080; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">GEO ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/place/GEO ID</div>
<div style="background-color: #ffcc00; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">ARCHIVES</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of papyrus archives with a unique Trismegistos Archives number (ARCH ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #ffcc00; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">ARCH ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/archive/ARCH ID</div>	<div style="background-color: #000080; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">EDITORS</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Database of modern editors with a unique Trismegistos Edit number (EDIT ID)</div> <div style="background-color: #000080; color: white; padding: 2px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">EDIT ID</div> <div style="padding: 2px;">-> http://www.trismegistos.org/editor/EDIT ID</div>

The online version of Trismegistos works with MySQL and PHP, but for data entry a set of relational Filemaker databases are used, currently in a mixed Filemaker 12-13 environment. The core of the database is Trismegistos Texts, where each individual record is identified by a unique, stable Trismegistos number. This number is used to link to most of the other constituent databases of Trismegistos and allows for easy implementation of one-to-many and many-to-one relationships. https://www.trismegistos.org/about_databasestructure.php Data and description: The core component of TM is Trismegistos Texts, currently counting 952619 entries. According to the scope of our survey, it is important to indicate that Trismegistos hosts the thematic database called Magic (<https://www.trismegistos.org/magic/>) that tries to fill a gap between projects such as the LDAB, HGV and BCD by collecting metadata of somewhat "dubious" nature: all things "religion", "ritual", "magic" and "divination" / "mantike". It contains 2491 records.

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Data model: it uses different standards (es.
<https://www.trismegistos.org/dataservices/rdf/per/index.php>)

Output: csv, json, jpg by means of the original repository.

How to use data: Content provided through the website and database is made available to all subject to a creative commons license (SS-BY-SA license)

Extraction of dataset: The user can use the search function typing the keywords in full, or it is possible to type keywords in different boxes such as Name/Editions/Catalogues, Editor, Edition date, Inventory, Material, Language(script), Provenance, Date, Reuse, Ancient Author&work, Type, (Ancient) Archive.

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Schloen J. D. & Schloen S. R. (2012). *Ochre : an online cultural and historical research environment*. Eisenbrauns.

Zamacona, C. G., & García, J. O. (2021). Digital Egyptology: a very short introduction. *y IP address 192.168. 10.17 on 2023/04/24*, 9.

4 Sitography

Digital Archives:

<https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/isac-integrated-database-project-idb>

<https://collezioni.museoegizio.it/>

<https://mann-napoli.it/collezioni/>

https://www.culturaitalia.it/opencms/museid/index_museid.jsp?language=it

https://www.culturaitalia.it/opencms/ricerca.jsp?q=*%&cat=indice&language=en

<http://demo-movio-musem.gruppometa.it/en/1/Home>

<https://papyri.info/>

<http://paths.uniroma1.it/>

<https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/projects/mummy-label-database-mld>

<https://corpus.louvre.fr/s/corpus/page/accueil>

<http://dlib.nyu.edu/ancientworld/>

<https://arachne.dainst.org/>

<http://sith.huma-num.fr/karnak>

<https://www.arnoldmeijer.nl/index.html>

<http://dasi.cnr.it/>

http://egyptologyresources.x10host.com/er/bibliography/bibliography_data.html

<https://www.propylaeum.de/en/subjects/reception-of-antiquity-in-a-semantic-network-digital-books-images-and-objects/research>

<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/cgi/i/image/image-idx?c=kelsey;page=index;sid=6feb1qk55vk7wjgzg3pmxlh59rv5dlgewd9jem5nrt4w;g=um-i>

<https://mudira.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/>

<https://coptos.mom.fr/>

<https://www.penn.museum/collections/>

Associated project to RESILIENCE

<https://www.dbmnt.uw.edu.pl/>

<https://www.betamasaheft.uni-hamburg.de/>

<https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

<https://opencontext.org/>

<https://www.brooklynmuseum.org/opencollection/collections/5>

<https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection>

<https://core.tdar.org/>

https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/sammlung/slg_1050/

<http://www.griffith.ox.ac.uk/archive/onlineresources/index.html>

<https://artmuseum.princeton.edu/search/collections>

<https://art.thewalters.org/browse/category/>; <https://www.thedigitalwalters.org/>

<https://museum.imj.org.il/Imagine/collections/index.asp#ImaginativeAccess>

<https://www.artic.edu/collection>

<https://collections.lacma.org/>

<https://cudl.lib.cam.ac.uk/collections/ethiopianmanuscripts/1>

<https://www.metmuseum.org>

<https://www.rmo.nl/en/collection/search-collection/>

<https://www.apd.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/apd/project.jsp>

<https://www.trismegistos.org/about.php>

Standards:

<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/> 19-12-2023

<https://www.dublincore.org/> 19-12-2023

<https://tei-c.org/>

<https://epidoc.stoa.org/>

<https://www.beniculturali.it/open-data-e-linked-data>

<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/home-2>

<https://auctions.nomismaweb.com/>

<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>

<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mods/>

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<https://epidoc.stoa.org/>

<https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

<https://pleiades.stoa.org/>

<https://client.perio.do/>

<https://iconclass.org/>

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